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1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of Sol2H2O¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D1.3 - Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

This report constitutes the final document on Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) activities carried out within the scope of the Sol2H2O.

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation is an important part of the Horizon Europe projects that all partners must take part in. Communicating European projects should aim at how research and innovation are contributing to an “Innovation Union”.

The initial DEC Plan (D1.3) defined a structured strategy to:

- Dissemination activities (making results public): targeting not only the scientific community but also the members of the 4Helix which might learn/use project results in the advancement of the State of the Art (policy makers, industry, civil society), these actions rely in FAIR and Open Access principles and took place from the moment the project starts producing results, until the project end. Examples of such activities include, e.g. scientific publications or communications, or experimental datasets;
- Exploitation activities (make concrete use of results): targeting the stakeholders which might take part in the exploitation of the project results towards the foreseeable outcomes (e.g. industry in the development of new products and/or services, policymakers in the definition of new regulations, value chain actors in the implementation of new business models), these actions might rely in the Protection of Intellectual Property and take place from the end of the project (or as soon as there are exploitable results). Examples of such activities include, e.g. roadmaps, patents, prototypes, regulatory recommendations, experimental datasets;
- Communication activities (promote actions and results): targeting a widespread audience (stakeholders, citizens) and at engaging with stakeholders, experts, market and public as to raise awareness and show the success of European collaboration, these actions rely on public media (social media, web-based communication, TV, radio, newspapers) and take place from the moment the project starts until its end. Examples of such activities include, e.g. website, newsletters, TV or radio interviews or newspaper articles.

Throughout the implementation period, a comprehensive set of actions was carried out, effectively engaging all four sectors of the 4Helix Innovation Model: academia, industry, civil society, and policymakers. Activities included scientific publications, participation in international conferences, technical and public events, media and web presence and the launch of proposals for further research and industrial collaboration.

Key outcomes include:

- Over seven peer-reviewed scientific publications;
- Participation and organisation of technical and scientific events;
- Launch and maintenance of an institutional website with more than 2500 unique visits;
- Active social media engagement with over 947 followers;

This plan is divided into 2 complementary components:

¹ Project: 101079305 — Sol2H2O — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

- Dissemination and communication activities, oriented to show the attractiveness of the results achieved and their impact towards a target audience composed of key stakeholders already identified;
- Exploitation actions, establishing the main pillars for the market uptake of the results generated in the project, maximising the opportunities for innovation and business.

This report details the activities carried out, the indicators achieved, materials produced, lessons learned and recommendations for the future, reflecting the consortium's commitment to scientific excellence, societal impact, and sustainable innovation.

2. DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION

A fundamental pillar of Sol2H2O was the integration of a DEC Plan, which recognised that scientific progress alone is insufficient without visibility, public engagement and sustainable use of results. As such, the DEC strategy was not an afterthought or accessory, it was a core horizontal component, deeply embedded across all work packages (WPs).

Oriented to show the attractiveness of the results achieved and their impact towards a target audience composed of key stakeholders already identified, the Dissemination and Communication strategy of Sol2H2O combined online and offline channels and tools, allowing the project to reach its different audiences.

Project dissemination aimed at maximising the extent to which key external stakeholders can use the project's results and outcomes, e.g. thorough scientific publications or communications or experimental datasets, supporting collaboration among key actors in the acceleration of the clean energy transition.

Project communication aimed at raising general awareness and support to Sol2H2O activities and its technological focus on Solar-driven WP&WT, as well as their relation to the Green Deal, Clean Energy Transition, and EU-funded research. As a display of the success of European collaboration, these actions relied on public media (social media, web-based communication, TV, radio, newspapers).

Aiming at the ensuing exploitation of the project results, an updated exploitation strategy envisaging a clear definition of project Key Exploitable results has also been developed.

This report presents the final implementation and evaluation of the Sol2H2O Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication strategy. It covers the full project duration (36 months), including:

- Objectives and strategic rationale behind the DEC activities;
- Methodologies and tools adopted to reach diverse audiences;
- Actions implemented across all three pillars (D, E, C);
- Engagement across the 4 Helix: Academia, Industry, Civil Society and Policymakers;
- Lessons learned.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE DEC PLAN

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan defined in the early stages of the Sol2H2O project (Deliverable D1.3) aimed to ensure that the project's scientific outputs, technological advancements and societal contributions would be effectively shared, promoted and capitalised upon across a diverse range of stakeholders.

The DEC strategy followed a structured approach to outreach, targeting the four main actors of the innovation ecosystem — Academia, Industry, Policy Makers and Civil Society — across three levels of influence: Regional, National and International. The DEC activities were revised in all the project meetings in order to monitor the accomplishment of the objectives.

3.1 Dissemination Objectives

- To promote Sol2H2O's scientific and technical results within the academic and research communities, through peer-reviewed publications, conference participation and open-access deliverables.
- To ensure that knowledge generated by the project would contribute to the state of the art, enabling future research and innovation in the water-energy nexus.
- To foster collaboration and networking with other R&I initiatives, including those under Horizon Europe, Water Europe, EDS and Water4All.

3.2 Communication Objectives

- To raise public awareness about the project's objectives, activities and expected impacts, with tailored messages for non-technical audiences.
- To use digital platforms (website, social media, email marketing) and traditional media (press releases) to share project updates, events and outcomes regularly.

3.3 Exploitation Objectives

- To promote the uptake of research results by industrial stakeholders, including SMEs and technology developers operating in the energy sector.
- To establish conditions for the valorisation of the project's outputs, including through Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management, technology transfer and the creation of spin-off opportunities.
- To leverage project results into future funding opportunities, such as Horizon Europe collaborative projects, Portugal 2030, or regional programs (e.g., Alentejo 2030).
- To develop PhD theses and start-up blueprints rooted in the project's Joint Research Activities (JRA), reinforcing sustainability beyond the project lifetime.

3.4 Monitoring Objectives

A robust monitoring mechanism (based on KPIs) was implemented to track the effectiveness of DEC actions, enabling real-time adjustments and improved decision-making upon the recurrent update of:

- "Sol2H2O_Scope and Success Criteria" (Figure 3.4.1) to monitor Task 5.1 and Task 5.2 KPI's/targets along with each project meeting revision, and
- "Sol2H2O_Social Networks, Newsletter, Website and Scientific Publications", monitoring the number of followers, subscribers, visitors, visualisations, and downloads, respectively, month by month, as well as the number of scientific publications with the project acknowledgement.

Success Criteria									
Task	Leader	Objectives	Scope	KPIs / Targets	M14	M22	M27	M30	M36
Additional RSF in Palermo									
National Water-Energy Strategy Symposium organization									
National Water-Energy Strategy Symposium participation				15-25/26-40/+40 (good/very good/excellent)			registrations: 74, total: 55; external: 40; industrial: 22; new participants: 38		
International Energy Transition Symposium organization								Portugal Day	
International Energy Transition Symposium participation				25-50/51-75/+75 (good/very good/excellent)				16 participants (9 voting) in the Portuguese Day	27 participants (22 voting) in the Spanish Day; 7 participants (6 voting) in the Italian Day; International day - registrations: 43; total: 48; external: 34; industrial: 21
5.2: Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC)	UEVORA	To develop, maintain, and execute a Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation, and communication (DEC) that maximises the project's results, outcomes, and impacts			4	0	EDS24 + EDS25	EDS24 + EDS25	
Corporate identity established				Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Social Media accounts				Yes (4)	4	4	3	3	
Social Media followers after 24 months				200-400/400-600/+600 (good/very good/excellent)	196	561	725	852	
Website established				Yes, with updates	Yes	Yes	Yes		
Website visitors				1000-2000/2000-3000/+3000 (good/very good/excellent)	218	720	1511	2098	
Press releases and mentions in mass-media				2-4/5-10/+10 (good/very good/excellent)	0	PREPARE PR & ORGANIZE EVE	1	2	
Sol2H2O email				Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Brochure and poster				No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
DEC Plan (D1.3)				Yes, with updates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Newsletters published				At least 4	2	6	9	10	
Newsletter and contact list subscriptions				100-200/200-400/+400 (good/very good/excellent)	76	92	108	148	
Zenodo downloads				10/30/50 (good/very good/excellent)	0	389	814	1606	

Figure 3.4.1: “Sol2H2O_Scope and Success Criteria” file: Task 5.1 and 5.2 KPI’s/target monitoring along project meetings

These objectives provided the foundation for the DEC activities carried out throughout the project and are assessed in terms of implementation and impact in the following sections of this report.

4. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS, ACTIVITIES AND TOOLS

The implementation of the Sol2H2O Dissemination and Communication strategy was underpinned by a structured and adaptive methodology. This approach ensured coherence across the three DEC pillars, alignment with project milestones and the ability to respond to evolving stakeholder needs throughout the project lifecycle. The methodology combined strategic planning with practical tools.

Having English as reference communication language, all the contents were translated - at the expense and responsibility of the corresponding partners - to the national languages of the partners involved in the Consortium: Portuguese (UEVORA), Spanish (CIEMAT and ITC) and Italian (UNIPA).

Dissemination and Communication activities were coordinated within the Consortium by a communication manager, coordinating the interaction among the partners, implementing and monitoring the strategy and acting as the main contact of reference for media and journalists.

From the outset, the DEC implementation was coordinated through a dedicated work package (WP5), led by the University of Évora. Regular coordination meetings ensured that activities were synchronised with the project's technical and scientific milestones.

A detailed workplan for DEC activities, aligned with the project Gantt chart, was defined (Deliverable 1.3).

Coordination of the DEC tasks was supported by online collaborative tools such as Google Drive, which enabled transparent access to media assets and planning documents.

4.1. Target audience

The identification of target audiences of the Sol2H2O project allowed customising the messages and dissemination & communication activities to every different group.

Table 4.1.1 presents the audience and stakeholders of the sector that have been identified before the start of the project. During the project, partners shared contacts, networking and activities established with these groups.

Table 4.1.1: Target audience and message in different Dissemination and Communication Channels

Target Groups	Specific Message	Communication Channels
1. ETIPs (European technology innovation platforms), IWGs (international working groups) and/or similar fora: in particular, in the field of Desalination, Water Treatment and Renewable Energies.	Collaborating to create holistic solutions involving two or more renewable energy technologies will increase impacts.	Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals; Events; Newsletter
2. Policy Makers: at the regional, national, and European levels.	Policies that support the development and deployment of Sol2H2O technologies as part of sustainable Water-Energy systems will accelerate the energy transition.	Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals; Events; Newsletter
3. Financial Actors: Examples include the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) and European Investment Bank.	Integrated water-energy systems that include Sol2H2O solutions are financially viable and profitable and result in a “green label” that is increasingly supported by the society at large.	Press releases; Events
4. Technology suppliers and end-users: EPCs (engineering, procurement and construction), technology developers and manufacturers, suppliers, end-users, plant managers, industrial associations.	Technology suppliers: large markets exist for Solar-driven WP&WT solutions (PV-RO, ST-MD, ZLD, AOP). End users: for Solar-driven WP&WT is uniquely positioned to deliver circular solutions to support sustainable water use in industries and businesses.	Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals; Events; Newsletter
5. R&D Funding Agencies: European Commission, National R&D funding, Regional development funding..	Investing in R&I that creates solutions that include Solar-driven WP&WT solutions as part of larger Water-Energy nexus systems will strengthen industrial capacities and competitiveness and grow economies at regional, national, and European levels.	Scientific journals; Meetings; Conferences
6. European Scientific Community: in particular, the Water Joint Programme Initiative (Water JPI).	The clean energy transition requires collaboration among stakeholders from both water and renewable energy technologies to develop holistic solutions.	Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals; Events; Newsletter
7. Basin regulators and Water Regulatory Authorities: both national and European.	Sol2H2O technologies can increase the performance and reliability of integrated renewable energy solutions.	Press releases; Scientific journals; Events
8. Global Scientific Community: in particular, the IEA TCPs SolarPACES, SHC.	Europe is a global R&I leader in creating systemic clean energy transition solutions that include Solar-driven WP&WT solutions	Web and social media; Press releases; Scientific journals; Events; Newsletter; Fast-Track

Target Groups	Specific Message	Communication Channels
	and wants to collaborate with other global leaders to support the clean energy transition.	Schools
9. General Public: at local, regional, national, European, and global levels.	The general public benefits from holistic clean energy transition solutions that include Solar-driven WP&WT.	Web and social media; Newsletter; Media Forum

4.2 Monitoring and KPI tracking tools

To assess the effectiveness of the DEC activities and facilitate continuous improvement, a suite of monitoring tools was deployed:

- Jetpack² for WordPress: To track website traffic;
- Social media analytics (native dashboards): To monitor followers, impressions, interactions and visualisations;
- Mailing list statistics: For newsletters and targeted updates;
- Event registration and feedback forms: Distributed digitally at outreach and training events.

4.3 Digital and physical tools

The DEC activities made use of a variety of professional tools and platforms, including:

Table 4.3.1: Digital and physical communication tools

Tool	Purpose
WordPress (website)	Website management and content updates
Canva	Design of posters, brochures and social media posts
YouTube	Hosting of video materials
Zoom Colibri	Online events
Mailchimp	Newsletter campaigns
Local/National media	Radio interviews, regional press coverage

All digital content was archived on Google Drive³.

5. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The dissemination component of Sol2H2O aimed to ensure that the knowledge, methodologies, and results generated throughout the project would be shared widely and effectively within the European and international scientific community. Dissemination was primarily targeted at researchers, academic institutions, technical platforms and R&D infrastructures.

Dissemination activities were carried out through multiple channels, including peer-reviewed publications, conference presentations, training and open access repositories.

² <https://cloud.jetpack.com>

³

5.1 Scientific publications and open access

One of the core objectives under the dissemination pillar was to publish scientific outputs in peer-reviewed journals with open access whenever possible. By the end of the project, Sol2H2O had produced and submitted seven peer-reviewed articles. Besides that, the project has two articles in the scope of Sol2H2O, but doesn't have the project's acknowledgement.

All publications were deposited in an open-access repository, Zenodo⁴. Metadata and datasets were shared following FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). We did not use the alternative repository (OpenAIRE), which had been considered as an alternative, since Zenodo worked smoothly and offered the additional advantage of enabling the publication not only of documents but also of research data. Another important aspect is the long-term preservation commitment of Zenodo: once deposited, materials are intended to be stored permanently, as Zenodo is operated by CERN and supported by the European OpenAIRE programme, ensuring sustainability and reliability for the future.

A full list of publications, with DOIs and links, is included in **Appendix 2** of this report.

5.2 Participation in scientific conferences

Another key dissemination avenue was active participation in national and international conferences.

These events provided key opportunities to:

- Present project results;
- Engage in technical discussions and establish collaborations;
- Connect with potential users of the platform and contributors to future research projects.

Participation was tracked and reported internally, with abstracts, presentations and proceedings archived for future reference.

Table 5.2.1: UÉVORA participation in scientific conferences

Date	Event	Location
15 and 16-11-2022	SUPEERA: Bringing research and industry closer	Almería, Spain
02-02-2024	ITI Water and Landscape Ecosystems Action Plan	São Bartolomeu de Messines, Portugal
27 to 30-04-2025	European Desalination Society	Porto, Portugal
24 and 25-09-2025	3rd Energy and Water Innovation & Technology Trade Show	Porto, Portugal

5.3 Fast-Track Schools

As part of the project's capacity-building effort, three Fast-Track Schools (FTS) were organised in Palermo, Pozo Izquierdo and Évora (Deliverable 3.1). These were short, intensive training events targeting Candidate and Young Researchers and technical staff from partner institutions and external organisations.

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/sol2h2o/records>

The events were supported by a structured dissemination plan. Before each FTS, invitations were circulated via email to previous participants and to members of the project mailing list. Announcements were included in the project newsletters published ahead of the schools, complemented by posts on social media inviting participation, and a dedicated news item on the project website.

84 participants attended the schools, including students of different nationalities from both EU and non-EU member states. Feedback collected from participants showed high levels of satisfaction.

During the events, photos were taken and shared in real time through Instagram stories, helping to engage the online community. After each FTS, a news article was published on the project website, accompanied by social media posts featuring photos of the events, and highlighted again in the project newsletter, which redirected readers to the website. In the final edition, selected feedback from participants was also showcased in a dedicated social media post, reinforcing the impact and value of the initiative (Fig. 5.3.1).

These FTS were designed as scalable and replicable formats, and teaching materials were shared openly online, in the Sol2H2O Zenodo and website.

The sessions were recorded and made available on YouTube⁵, using the “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle.

A satisfaction survey was conducted after each FTS, and the results will be published on the website soon.

Figure 5.3.1: Fast-Track School Feedback

5.4 Water-Energy Strategy Symposium

This symposium was held at UEVORA with the presentation and discussion about the role of the Water-Energy Nexus in the objectives of the National Energy and Climate Plan, as well as the industrial development potential of different technological solutions for water production and treatment through solar energy (Deliverable 4.1). 55 participants attended this symposium.

The event was supported by a dedicated communication and dissemination strategy. Before the symposium, a “save the date” was circulated by email one to two months in advance, followed

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/@RenewableEnergiesChair/playlists>

by a special newsletter⁶ inviting participation. The project website featured a news item announcing the event, complemented by posts on social media and the dissemination of a press release to local, regional, national, and specialized media (Appendix 3). During the symposium, real-time updates were shared through Instagram stories, providing visibility and engagement with a wider audience. After the event, a news article with highlights was published on the project website, accompanied by social media posts featuring photos from the sessions. The symposium was also featured in the project newsletter. Also, the presentations were uploaded to Zenodo, ensuring open access and long-term availability of the materials.

In addition, an Italian symposium was held under the Sol2H2O project: the National Water-Energy Strategy Symposium, organized by UNIPA in collaboration with the newly formed Italian Association for Desalination and Water Reuse (AIDARA), took place at the University of Palermo on 1-2 July 2025. This two-day event addressed seawater desalination and related technologies in the context of the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus, bringing together stakeholders from policy, industry, civil society, research, and professional sectors. The symposium examined the state of desalination technologies, their applications at regional and national levels, current implementations, and future prospects; it also explored integration into circular economy models and assessed environmental, social, and economic sustainability aspects.

5.5 Water-Energy Transition Symposium

The international symposium “Water-Energy Transition” was held online in July, bringing together experts from academia, industry, and policy. The program included presentations on technological innovations in wastewater treatment, water production through desalination, and the valorization of brine from desalination processes.

The event also highlighted the results of national sessions held in Portugal, Spain, and Italy. Across the sessions, participants identified common challenges, including the economic costs of technologies, social perceptions, and regulatory barriers. They emphasized the need for a clear legal framework, effective communication, comprehensive economic studies, and stronger integration between water production, energy management, and circular economy models.

The symposium was organized locally in each of the three Consortium countries, with the first day dedicated to national discussions and the second day held online, where the main outcomes from each country were presented and debated in a joint round table (Deliverable 4.1). More than 48 participants attended the second day of the symposium.

Given its structure, communication was adapted to the two levels of the event. For the national sessions, invitations were sent in a targeted and personalized way, as these discussions were addressed to a more restricted audience in each country. Following these sessions, a news item was published on the project website and on social media.

For the final joint session, involving all three partners, a broader dissemination effort was made. Before the event, announcements were published on social media and in the project newsletter, inviting a wider audience to participate. After the session, a news article was made available on the project website, accompanied by social media posts. In addition, the presentation delivered during the joint session was uploaded to Zenodo, ensuring open access and long-term availability of the materials.

5.6 Regional Specialization Forum

In this context, four forums were held, as mentioned in Deliverable 4.1, which took place in Évora. These forums involved engaging Policy (Regional Development Coordination Commission, Intermunicipal Communities), Industry (Regional Development Association, Entrepreneurial

⁶ <https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/media-en/#newsletters>

Association, Sines Technopole), and Academia (Regional Universities and Polytechnic Institutes in Évora, Portalegre, and Beja) around the role of Sol2H2O technological solutions in the objectives of the Regional Smart Specialization Strategy.

A total of 32 participants took part.

Additionally, one Regional Specialization Forum organized by UNIPA was held in Palermo on the 3rd and 4th of April 2024, gathering around one hundred participants. The event brought together stakeholders from Academia, Policy Makers, Industry, Foundations, representatives of EU Initiatives, and Civil Society. The discussions focused on technological solutions for solar-driven desalination and water treatment, evaluating the feasibility of establishing value chains in Sicily and their alignment with the regional policy framework.

The fifth and final forum will take place in November 2025, in Portugal.

Each forum was supported by targeted communication and dissemination activities. Ahead of the events, announcements were published on social media, complemented by personalized email invitations sent to relevant stakeholders, and a dedicated news item was made available on the project website. During the last three sessions, with the hiring of the new communications manager, real-time engagement was ensured through Instagram stories, sharing moments and highlights with a broader audience. After the events, a follow-up news article was published on the project website, supported by social media posts showcasing the discussions. Additionally, the presentations delivered at the forums were uploaded to Zenodo, ensuring open and long-term access to the materials.

5.7 Scientific visibility and metrics

Table 5.7.1 and Figure 5.7.1 present quantitative and qualitative data that demonstrate the effectiveness of the dissemination efforts:

Table 5.7.1: Dissemination activities indicators

Tool/Action	Indicator: Level of success			Achieved
	Good	Very good	Excellent	
Fast-track Schools	15 registrations	20 registrations	>25 registrations	84
Water-Energy Strategy Symposium	15-25 registrations	26-40 registrations	>40 registrations	55
Water-Energy Transition Symposium	25-50 registrations	51-75 registrations	>75 registrations	45
Regional Specialization Fora	15-25 registrations	26-40 registrations	>40 registrations	32
Scientific Publications	4 publications	8 publications	12 publications	7
Conference participations	-	-	4 participations	4

Figure 5.7.1: Dissemination activities indicators and level of success

6. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

While dissemination targeted the scientific and technical community, communication activities were designed to reach broader, non-specialist audiences, ensuring that the project's work was visible, understandable and relevant to society at large. Effective communication served multiple purposes: to inform, inspire, educate and build public trust in science and technology.

6.1 Communication Strategy

Sol2H2O communication activities aim to raise awareness and foster support for the project's work on solar-driven water-related technologies, highlighting their relevance to the European Green Deal, the Clean Energy Transition, and EU-funded research. Communication actions relied on public media (social media, web-based communication, TV, radio, newspapers).

6.1.1 Website

The official Sol2H2O website (<https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/>) served as the central hub for all project communication. At the beginning of the project, a dedicated website was created to ensure visibility and provide regular updates on Sol2H2O's activities. In October 2023 (M11), the website was migrated to a new platform, which improved its functionality and accessibility. As a result, web statistics are only available from October 2023 onwards.

The site was designed with accessibility, responsiveness and clarity in mind, featuring dedicated sections for news, events, and open-access resources:

- Project overview and objectives;
- General information about the project (e.g. work packages);
- Description of all the organisations' members of the consortium;
- News updates;
- Media presence;
- Newsletters;

- Printable materials (brochure and roll-up);
- Links to scientific publications and public deliverables;
- Links to the social media channels;
- Addressing and contact information;
- Appropriate acknowledgement and reference to the European Union’s Horizon Europe Framework Programme and disclaimer excluding European Commission responsibility.

The website is available in English, Portuguese, Italian and Spanish, ensuring accessibility to local and international audiences alike. Regular updates kept stakeholders informed of events and outcomes.

Also, under the “Careers” menu, visitors will find three sections entitled “Living in...” (Deliverable 3.3), each offering insights into the regions where the project and its partners are based. Living in Alentejo introduces the cultural, social, and professional environment of southern Portugal, where the University of Évora plays a central role. Living in Sicily presents the Italian island context, highlighting its Mediterranean lifestyle, academic collaborations, and unique local opportunities. Living in Gran Canaria, on the Canary Islands in Spain, showcasing the advantages of living and working in an Atlantic island setting. Together, these pages are designed to give prospective researchers, collaborators, and international partners a clear picture of the living conditions and opportunities available across the partners' regions, emphasizing the diversity and mobility that the project encourages.

Figure 6.1.1.1: Sol2H2O “Careers” menu with “Living in...” section

In line with the Grant Agreement, the website will remain online for at least two years after the end of the project, ensuring continued access to information and materials produced.

Key statistics from website analytics:

- 2500+ unique visitors;
- 6000+ visualizations;
- Most viewed pages: Media and The Project.

Figure 6.1.1.2: Sol2H2O website visitors (M10 to M33)

The website experienced gradual growth, but from M22 to M23 the jump was bigger, linked to Fast-Track School #2, and it was precisely in M23 that the minimum KPI for website visitors was reached.

6.1.2 Social Media

Social media was a vital component of the communication mix, enabling real-time updates, two-way engagement and viral outreach. Instagram, X and LinkedIn accounts were created at M4 and YouTube on M11. Sol2H2O maintained active profiles on:

- X - @Sol2H2OHEUROPE
- LinkedIn⁷ - Sol2H2O
- YouTube - @RenewableEnergiesChair – Sol2H2O Playlist
- Instagram⁸ - @sol2h2o

Throughout the project, social network X consistently had the lowest engagement and audience reach. Additionally, its follower count was decreasing daily, possibly due to political reasons (Appendix 4). Therefore, during the project meeting #5 held in February 2025 at UEVORA, the consortium decided to deactivate this social network starting from February 2025.

Figure 6.1.2.1: Last publication on X

⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/sol2h2o/>

⁸ <https://www.instagram.com/sol2h2o>

Unlike Instagram and LinkedIn, on YouTube, the number of views of project-related videos was tracked rather than the number of subscribers. Since it is less common for users to subscribe to channels in this context, the consortium agreed that video views would provide a more accurate indicator of outreach and engagement. Therefore, even though the statistics tables formally refer to “followers,” in the case of YouTube, they actually reflect the cumulative views of Sol2H2O videos.

Instagram was not originally included in the project’s Grant Agreement, but it was later discussed and agreed within the consortium that creating an account on this platform would be valuable. The account was therefore launched, bringing additional visibility to the project, a positive outcome that not only contributed to achieving the social media KPIs but also helped reach audiences different from those on LinkedIn, as the two platforms are used by distinct communities with different purposes.

Achievements:

- Over 900+ followers across platforms;
- 150+ original posts published;
- Posts shared by partners.

Social media content was scheduled via Instagram, YouTube and LinkedIn platforms, supported by design templates made in Canva and in English (translated when needed).

On YouTube, the project video and videos from the Fast-Track Schools were published.

Achievements:

- 17 subscribers;
- 11 videos;
- 625 visualisations;
- Project Video with 48 visualisations.

Figure 6.1.2.2: Sol2H2O social media followers (M10 to M33)

Figure 6.1.2.3: Sol2H2O social media followers in M24

Month 24 is highlighted in Figure 6.1.2.2 because it corresponds to the KPI reference point. Up to that month, there had been a steady increase in followers across the different social media platforms, with the minimum target for social media already achieved at M15.

A list of some social media screenshots is included in **Appendix 4** of this report.

6.1.3 Newsletter and Mailings

Over the course of the project, 12 newsletters were published, with a thirteenth still to be released. These newsletters focused on presenting the project, advertising upcoming events, and summarising key results and outcomes. For the Water-Energy Strategy symposium, held in Évora in February 2025, a dedicated newsletter was sent in Portuguese to serve as both an invitation and an informational resource, as the event was conducted in that language.

The newsletters were published on the project website and social media and sent every two months.

Subscriptions were gathered through a registration form on the website, an existing contact list from the partners and through the consortium's participation in other EU initiatives, events, fairs, workshops and similar activities.

The newsletter has a total of 195 contacts, with four having unsubscribed. Of the current subscribers, 59 signed up through the website or subscription link, while the remaining 136 were added by the project following events where participants agreed to receive the newsletter.

Figure 6.1.3.1: Sol2H2O newsletter subscribers (M11 to M33)

The first newsletter was sent out in M11, although the Mailchimp account had been created one month earlier, in M10. Since there had been no events prior to that moment from which subscribers could be collected, those who subscribed before the launch did so either via the website or through direct invitation.

The subscriber base grew gradually, with the minimum KPI being achieved in M23. At each subsequent event, new subscribers were added, and some also joined through word of mouth, subscribing directly via the project’s website. A noticeable increase was observed from 163 to 195 subscribers in M27, coinciding with the Water-Energy Strategy symposium in Portugal.

Mailings with invitations to relevant events and other information which cannot wait for the newsletter publication or that cannot appear only in the newsletter will be sent out to the same database used for the newsletter.

Through the use of an online tool (Mailchimp), frequent news and achievements were shared to raise awareness of and support for the Sol2H2O action.

A full list of links to access the Newsletter is included in **Appendix 5** of this report.

6.1.4 Events

The events were one of the most important parts of the dissemination and communication strategy because they allow connections with stakeholders, encourage networking and show advances and results of the project. Events also fed content to the communication channels and tools (website, social media, press releases), generating impacts on different audiences.

The strategy of participation in events will be set up at two different levels:

- Joining events organised by other key institutions/organisations;
- Events organised and promoted by Sol2h2O, collaborating with other initiatives and organisations to generate synergies.

- **Presence and Reporting on Key Events**

Partners of the consortium attended relevant events, conferences, etc., like EDS.

International events were one of the most effective dissemination and communication actions to reach the different stakeholders. The partners' participation in events generated more visibility for the Sol2H2O project and boosted contact with stakeholders and other European projects.

The project was also presented at international events like the ENERH2O Trade Show⁹ (Porto – Portugal).

Figure 6.1.4.1: Sol2H2O ENERH2O participation confirmation on the trade show website

- **Organisation of Sol2H2O Events**

As part of the Sol2H2O project, three symposia and Regional Specialization Forum were organised.

6.1.5 Press releases and Media

Relationships with the media were established through the Sol2H2O communication manager. This task was accomplished at the national and regional levels in Portugal.

Throughout the project, eight official press releases were prepared and distributed to communicate the national symposium - Water-Energy Strategy (before and after), the Italian Water-Energy Strategy symposium, the Spanish day of the international symposium - Water-Energy Transition¹⁰, the international symposium (after), one about the Fast-Track Schools and the presence at ENERH2O - 3rd ENERGY AND WATER INNOVATION & TECHNOLOGY TRADE SHOW (before and after).

In addition, an opinion article by Pedro Horta, the project coordinator, was published in the July/August edition of the specialized magazine *Aspectos*¹¹, under the theme "Decarbonization and the use of alternative water resources" (Figure 6.1.5.2).

⁹ <https://www.enerh2o.com/>

¹⁰ www.aguasresiduales.info/revista/noticias/resumen-y-conclusiones-del-xiv-congreso-internacio-Oaz8n

¹¹ <https://www.calameo.com/read/004601149403cdd3641b8>

In the Media

[Projeto Europeu Sol2H2O organiza simpósio nacional sobre Água e Energia em Évora](#)

[Sol2H2O organiza simpósio nacional sobre Água e Energia em Évora](#)

[Projeto Europeu Sol2H2O organiza simpósio nacional sobre Água e Energia em Évora](#)

[Universidade de Évora promove simpósio nacional sobre Água e Energia](#)

[Água e energia no 'centro' de simpósio nacional "Water-Energy Strategy"](#)

[Simpósio "Water-Energy Strategy" debate desafios e soluções para o futuro do tratamento da água em Portugal](#)

[Évora: Simpósio "Water-Energy Strategy" debate desafios e soluções para o futuro do tratamento da água em Portugal](#)

[Simpósio "Water-Energy Strategy" debate desafios e soluções para o futuro do tratamento da água em Portugal](#)

[Évora: Simpósio "Water-Energy Strategy" debate desafios e soluções para o futuro do tratamento da água em Portugal](#)

[Resumen y conclusiones del "XIV Congreso Internacional de AEDyR" celebrado en Tenerife del 24 al 26 de junio](#)

[A descarbonização e a utilização de recursos hídricos alternativos](#)

[Simpósio Internacional debate nexa Água-Energia](#)

[Mais de 40 entidades reunidas em simpósio internacional sobre Água e Energia organizado pela Universidade de Évora](#)

[Simpósio internacional "Water-Energy Transition" dedicado à transição energética no setor da Água](#)

[Universidade de Évora leva inovação energética e hídrica à feira ENERH2O no Porto](#)

[Projetos da Universidade de Évora em destaque na feira internacional ENERH2O](#)

[Évora: Jovens investigadores capacitados em energias renováveis e soluções solares para a água](#)

[Capacitação de jovens investigadores em transição energética e água](#)

[UE leva inovação à ENERH2O](#)

Figure 6.1.5.1: Media presence on the Sol2H2O website

Figure 6.1.5.2: Opinion article in Aspectos magazine

A full list of press releases with links is included in **Appendix 6** of this report.

Impact: At least 20 mentions in regional media outlets, including both print and digital newspapers.

By the end of the project, one additional press release is planned, about the Sol2H2O pilot in Évora. In this way, we will have a total of nine press releases by the end of the project.

6.1.6 Branding, Visual Identity and Materials

To ensure consistency and recognisability, a unified project visual identity was applied across all communication materials. The branding package included:

- Sol2H2O logo and colour palette;
- PowerPoint templates;
- Roll-up and brochure;
- Hashtags;
- Social media visual guidelines;
- Email signature template;
- Newsletter.

6.1.6.1 Sol2H2O logo and colour palette

The logo represents Sol2H2O vision on the use of Solar-driven WP&WT (in orange) as a "hub" for water production and treatment (in blue).

The project also has the logo all in white, black and only the symbol. (<https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/media-en/#communication-materials>).

All communication materials used them consistently to ensure brand recognition and coherence.

6.1.6.2 PowerPoint templates

A general PowerPoint presentation was created to align presentations with the Sol2H2O visual identity, ensuring coherence in structure, fonts and colours. The PPT presentation was used and completed by the partners of the consortium.

Figure 6.1.6.2.1: PowerPoint template

6.1.6.3 Roll-up and brochure

A roll-up banner and flyers were designed for promotional use at physical events, maintaining the established branding elements.

A roll-up was created using the project's colour palette and the water-treatment pilot image, featuring the logos of the project partners and the European Union, the Grant Agreement (GA) number, and a QR code directing people to the official website.

The flyer was designed in a tri-fold format, targeting the general public and presenting the most relevant information about the project. It includes the project duration, the water-treatment pilot image, the concept and objectives, the mentoring programme (formerly known as Living Amenities), a QR code linking to the website, the logos of the project partners and the European Union, along with the GA number, and contact details, including another QR code for subscribing to the newsletter via the website. A total of 100 paper copies were printed and distributed at the Fast-Track Schools, Project Meetings, Energy-Strategy symposium, and internal events of the widening partner.

The design of the roll-up and brochure is in **Appendix 7** of this report.

6.1.6.4 Hashtags

An official hashtag, #Sol2H2O was created to reinforce the project's identity across social media platforms and promote community engagement.

6.1.6.5 Social media visual guidelines

Social media templates and visual guidelines were developed to ensure that posts on platforms such as Instagram, LinkedIn, and X consistently reflect the project's brand identity.

Initially, a single template was considered for use across all posts. However, it was later decided that this approach could make the pages appear too repetitive and visually unengaging. Instead, a more flexible approach was adopted, aiming to create diverse posts tailored to each topic, while still maintaining brand consistency. Most of the posts included the project logo and used the same typography. Two fonts were selected: Oswald, used in the flyer and website, and Poppins, specifically chosen for social media content.

6.1.6.6 Email signature template

A branded email signature was developed to unify professional communications and strengthen brand perception. This signature was used throughout the Sol2H2O project's official email communications.

With our best wishes,
Sol2H2O coordination.

Figure 6.1.6.6.1: Email signature template

6.1.6.7 Newsletter

A newsletter design was created for the project, incorporating the logos of the partners, the European Union emblem and the Grant Agreement (GA) number, as well as the project logo. The newsletter consistently followed the same layout: a blue title, an image accompanied by text, and, when relevant, a button linking to the full news article on the website. The design also included links to the project's social media accounts and an "unsubscribe" button.

Figure 6.1.6.7.1: Newsletter design

6.1.6.8 Project Video¹²

In February 2025, during the project meeting held at the University of Évora, a short and engaging video was recorded to present Sol2H2O. In just a few minutes, the video clearly and concisely explains the project's purpose, combining images of the facilities of the widening partner with short testimonials from each Work Package (WP) leader.

The footage highlights the research environment and infrastructures at UEVORA, underlining the project's scientific and technological excellence. Each WP leader briefly presents their role: from overall coordination, through scientific and technical development, impact assessment, and alignment with energy policies. This format provides a quick yet comprehensive overview of Sol2H2O's main objectives and its collaborative structure.

Figure 6.1.6.8.1: Project video

¹² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tGojcJZHw3c>

6.1.7 Zenodo Repository

Sol2H2O's Research Infrastructure (RI) and Joint Research Activities (JRA) results were presented in peer-reviewed journals and, following the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary," the articles were made available online via Zenodo, a free and open-access repository approved by the European Commission.

Figure 6.1.7.1: Sol2H2O Zenodo

The Sol2H2O website (www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt) provides information about the scientific publications.

The Sol2H2O community on Zenodo currently includes 47 publications, encompassing both scientific papers and project-related presentations.

So far, the community has recorded around **2416** downloads, of which **323** downloads correspond to scientific publications that include Sol2H2O acknowledgement, **116** downloads of the public deliverables published (2.1 - Solar-driven water production, water treatment and zero-liquid discharge solutions and 3.2 - PhD Programs), **445** downloads on the papers published and **1532** on the presentations from Fast-Track Schools, symposia and Regional Specialization Fora.

It should be noted that download statistics are only accounted for from M18 onwards, as this was when publications started being uploaded to Zenodo and tracking began.

Figure 6.1.7.1: Sol2H2O Zenodo cumulative downloads (M18 to M33)

Figure 6.1.7.2: Sol2H2O Zenodo downloads by category

6.1.8 Mentoring Program¹³

A Mentoring Program was established to support partners, senior researchers, young researchers, and candidate young researchers during their stay in the widening partner's city, Évora. This initiative aimed to provide guidance, facilitate integration, and enhance the overall experience of those involved.

In total, there were six registrations for mentors and three registrations for mentees, as detailed in Deliverable 3.3.

6.2 Communication Results

Table 6.2.1 and Figure 6.2.1 present quantitative and qualitative data that demonstrate the effectiveness of the communication efforts:

Table 6.2.1: Communication activities indicators

¹³ <https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/mentoring-program/>

Tool/Action	Indicator: Level of success			Achieved
	Good	Very good	Excellent	
Roll-Up/brochure	Available online	Available online and distributed in Fast-Track Schools	Available online and distributed at Sol2H2O events	Available online and distributed at Sol2H2O events
Announcements and Newsletters	100 - 200 subscribers	200 - 400 subscribers	>400 subscribers	195 subscribers
Sol2H2O website	1.000 - 2.000 visitors	2.000 - 3.000 visitors	>3.000 visitors	2480 visits
Social Media	200 - 400 followers after 24 months	400 - 600 followers after 24 months	>600 followers after 24 months	947
Press releases and mentions in mass media	2 - 4	5 - 10	>10	8
Zenodo Repository	10 downloads	30 downloads	50 downloads	2416
Mentoring Program	5 subscriptions	15 subscriptions	30 subscriptions	9

Figure 6.2.1: Communication activities indicators and level of success

7. EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

Project exploitation aimed at the concrete use of project results and at strengthening their competitive position as new business/service opportunities. Within the scope of the project, Key Exploitable Results (KERs) were defined around:

1. enhanced collaborations amongst consortium members;
2. expanded networks;
3. enhanced scientific profiles;
4. stronger policy and regulatory support;
5. increased R&I support; and
6. better alignment of R&I activities and funding with industrial needs.

Along the project one main Key Exploitation Result has been identified: the use of the Research Infrastructure as a driver for innovation. Included in the “features” of this KER, a clear vision on how can support to innovation around Sol2H2O “beyond state-of-the-art” concept (as presented in Deliverable 2.1) can be provided not only through the upgraded and distributed RI developed in the project (see Deliverable 2.2), but also through further investment in material and technical support to innovation related aspects to be made available to RI users.

For the later, a concrete concept has been developed and is under use along with a financing strategy aiming at the further development of the infrastructure along its lines: facilities for short term incubation, RI interpretative center, investor visits, market and supply chain assessment support, guidelines and documental support to startup funding rounds.

7.1. KER identification and assessment

Following Sol2H2O exploitation methodology, covering all the steps required for the innovation process:

- the identification of the problem addressed;
- the assessment of the suitability of the result as a solution;
- the definition of the most suitable IP protection requirements/strategy;
- the identification of a “minimum viable version” enabling its test/demonstration;
- the identification of the relevant stakeholders and;
- the definition of a concrete business model and required funding sources,

a clear definition of the KER and a due assessment of its uniqueness, interest and exploitation route has been achieved, as follows.

7.1.1 Identification of KERs

Along Sol2H2O Joint Research Activity, two main work “branches” were developed:

- A. the definition of a “Sol2H2O beyond SoA” concept, in Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 (see Deliverable 2.1);

- B. the implementation of Widening RI upgrades and e.infrastructure assets enabling remote and multi-site services with TOP partners' RI,

both of them potentially standing for KERs. Upon assessment of both options by the PSC:

- “Sol2H2O beyond SoA” concept presents the potential for multiple developments at both component, system and service levels, all of them implying the participation of production/marketing enabling competencies (industrial stakeholders);
- the use of the upgraded and distributed RI facilities in support to innovation along “Sol2H2O beyond SoA” concept (components, systems, services) entails not only the RI assets but also material and technical support to users in bridging the gap between TRL4-8/9.

This assessment led to the definition of one KER:

“Sol2H2O RI as a driver for technological innovation on the use of solar energy for water production and treatment”.

7.1.2.Problem/Solution identification

Based on the definition of a KER, a clear statement on the problem addressed and on the suitability of the KER a (or the) solution to address it, was validated upon:

- a clear statement on the problem which might be addressed by the KER: what is the problem, how/what is affected, what are the impacts (because PROBLEM, SOMETHING occurs to AFFECTED and results in IMPACT): *“The need for a CAPEX and OPEX intensive BoS enabling experimental validation of new desalination and water treatment technologies and components impairs their validation towards TRL 8-9.”;*
- identification of other possible solutions to the problem: companies developing new technologies, components or services develop in-house testing capabilities representative of realistic operation conditions (TRL5-7), which is only possible to a lesser extent (e.g. small scale components, validation with potential offtaker).

7.1.3. Identification of relevant Stakeholders

The identification of relevant stakeholders is key in the comprehension of how the KER can be turned into a product/service/solution – the innovation process. Relevant stakeholders include not only suppliers (of materials, services, know-how) or customers, but also all other actors which might play a role in the innovation process, as regulators, financial service providers, investors, labour, media, public administration, etc. In Sol2H2O KER context, the following stakeholders (and stakeholder matrix) have been identified:

Table 7.1 Sol2H2O KER relevant stakeholders

Stakeh.	Descrip.	Role (Influence) [Support]
1. Water Europe	Water Europe Technology & Innovation	Water Europe is the leading European multi-stakeholder association that drives innovation, research, and technology development in the water sector to achieve a Water-Smart Society, where water is managed sustainably for security, resilience, and the circular economy. Its role involves advocating for water as a policy priority, facilitating collaboration among over 250 members, influencing EU policy and funding programs, and promoting knowledge exchange to build a water-resilient Europe.promoter of water-related innovation, research, and technology development in Europe.

Stakeh.	Descrip.	Role (Influence) [Support]
		With a focus on the entire water value chain, Water Europe advocates for building a water secure, sustainable, and resilient, Water-Smart Society across Europe and beyond. (Governance, services, IP and FAIR data, communication: HIGH) [Widened scope for Water Techs as opportunity: POSITIVE]
2. Water RI Manag	RI managers @ Water RIs	Responsible for defining and implementing R&D and investment strategies, access procedures, technical staff team, and engaging with users and resident R&D groups. (Responsible for individual Water RIs development strategy and sustainability: HIGH) [Opportunity to cost reductions and scope users: POSITIVE]
3. Water RI Tech	RI Technical staff @ Water RIs	Responsible for O&M and R&D support in each Water RI, holding know-how on operations and contributing to reducing OPEX and environmental impacts. (Know-how on Water RIs O&M, critical to procedural changes: HIGH) [Opportunity to share know-how and O&M improvements: POSITIVE]
4. Water Industrial Eco	Industries and Ind. Assoc. in Water Tech+ value chain	Industries and Industrial Associations in the widened Water Tech value chain (membranes, pumps, hydraulic circuits) holding the know how and industrial capacity to development and marketing of new components/systems (Industrial capacity required to the production of Water related Tech Innovation: HIGH) [Willing to be part in new markets, regarded regulation is favorable: NEUTRAL]
5.ERICs/RIs	Complementary ERICs and National RIs	Complementary ERICs and other (national) RIs with expertise and RI assets on upstream (e.g. membranes development, chemistry) and downstream (energy efficiency, water distribution systems) Water Techs fields. (Synergies and widen cooperation strengthening the EU RI landscape: MODERATE) [Perceive cooperation in SALTIS scope as opportunity: POSITIVE]
6. Policy	Water Policy actors at National and EU level	Responsible for the implementation of water-related and environmental policies. Play roles in water governance, implementing policies, managing resources, and setting standards; provide technical and financial support, and influence water-related initiatives. (Water and Environmental policy makers at national and EU levels: HIGH) [Define market regulation enabling leveled playfield for technologies: NEUTRAL]
7. Bank/Inv	Financing institutions and Investors	Financing institutions help define bankability conditions for innovative technologies, while investors in new fields are key to leveraging concepts from start-ups or driving investment from established companies. (Actors in acquisition of CAPEX bringing innovation to TRLs 7-9: HIGH) [Investment in innovative ventures, if business case is demonstrated: NEUTRAL]

Stakeh.	Descrip.	Role (Influence) [Support]
8. Market	Water TEch end-users	Including utility-scale and industrial end-users, define market entry conditions for Water Tech products regarding competitiveness (e.g., with RO) and O&M requirements for swift adoption. (Establish the market pool for Water TEchs, enabling their passage to TRL9: HIGH) [Despite early-adopters - might present resistance to new supply chains: NEGATIVE]
9. R&D	Academia, R&D, Technology developers	Natural beholder of the scientific and technological know-how and prone to the development of innovation and technology transfer activities. (Ability to produce innovation but a less to define value chain: MODERATE) [Opportunity for technology transfer: POSITIVE]
10. Public	Consumers/ citizens	Citizens (general Public) act as both consumers and policy agents (electors) with an expectable influence over policies and market. (Consumers perception in the exploitation activities: MODERATE) [Perception of Water Tech as environmentally and economically beneficial: NEUTRAL]

The foregoing definition enables us to define the Stakeholders Influence/Support Matrix presented in Table 2.2.

Table 7.2 Sol2H2O stakeholders Influence/Support Matrix

Stakeholders Influence/Support matrix		Support		
		POSITIVE	NEUTRAL	NEGATIVE
INFLUENCE	HIGH	1. Water Europe, 2. Water RI Manag, 3. Water RI Tech,	4. Water Industrial Eco, 6. Policy, 7. Bank/Inv	8. Market
	MODERATE	5.ERICs/RIs, 9. R&D	10. Public	
	LOW			

7.1.4. Minimum viable version

The definition of a “minimum viable version” (MVV) for the KER test/validation as a suitable solution for the problem it addresses includes both the infrastructural assets, but also the material and technical innovation support assets required for an effective support to activities with RI users in the transition of TRL4-6 to TRL7-9.

A MVV of Sol2H2O KER entails, thus:

- the RI upgrade enabling the material implementation of services along Sol2H2O beyond SoA technological approach at component, system and service levels: as of Sol2H2O JRA results in Task 2.3 (see Deliverable 2.2);
- the operationalization of remote and multi-site services with partner RIs: as of Sol2H2O JRA results in Task 2.4 (see Deliverable 2.2);
- the definition and communication of an updated list of services: as of Sol2H2O JRA results in Tasks 2.3 and 2.4 (see Deliverable 2.2) and of EU-SOLARIS membership (Task 4.1, Deliverable);
- the availability of physical facilities at the RI enabling short-term incubation activities by industrial RI users (as e.g. startups) developing product development, demonstration or

showcasing to investors in RI environment: part of SOL4R INCUBATOR proposal (see Section 7.3);

- the availability of guidelines and support materials (templates) enabling the showcasing of products developed/demonstrated in the RI to investors in financing rounds: part of SOL4R INCUBATOR proposal (see Section 7.3);
- the implementation of a virtual interpretation center, enabling the presentation and framing of the RI and RI assets to investors and/or 4Helix visitors: part of SOL4R INCUBATOR proposal (see Section 7.3).

Aiming at the engagement of stakeholders, specific contacts and engagement statements have been defined, as presented in table 7.3.

Table 7.3 Sol2H2O KER stakeholder contacts and engagement rationale

Stakeh.	Contacts	Engagement statement
1. Water Europe	Water Europe and Water related RIs (CIEMAT, ITC, UNIPA)	Development of a coherent and coordinated innovation support structure and implementation of multi-site/remote services enables a wider scope of services and possibility of “cross-selling” of services
2. Water RI Manag	RI managers @ Water RIs (CIEMAT, ITC, UNIPA)	Development of coherent and coordinated R&D and investment strategies, access procedures, enables merging individual experiences and open the possibility of exchanging technical staff in peak activity periods
3. Water RI Tech	RI Technical staff @ Water RIs	Shared experience on O&M and R&D support in each Water RI widens individual know-how on MS operations and contributes to reducing RI OPEX and environmental impacts.
4. Water Industrial Eco	(non exhaustive list) Bondalti, Aqualia, AGS	Industries and Industrial Associations in the widened Water Tech value chain (membranes, pumps, reactors, chemical products) are supported in innovation prone to value the know how and industrial capacity in the development and marketing of new components/systems
5. ERICs/RIs	CERIC-ERIC, ECCSEL-ERIC, ESS ERIC	Exploitation of synergies with complementary ERICs with expertise and RI assets on upstream (e.g. turbomachinery, power electronics, chemistry) and downstream (sector coupling, energy efficiency, grid connection) contributes to wider scope of services and approach to interface R&D questions
6. Policy	ERSAR, APA, ARH Alentejo (non-exhaustive list)	Access to Water Tech competitiveness and market pool assessment, drafting their potential impacts on the water sector, provides technical insight into implementation of water-related and environmental policies and market framework fostering both the objectives of EU Water directives and EU Industrial Leadership and CRM strategies.
7. Bank/Inv	KfW, EIB, EU-startups database	Access to frontline product demonstration results and participate in the definition of bankability conditions for innovative technologies

Stakeh.	Contacts	Engagement statement
8. Market	utilities (e.g., AdP, Aqualia), industrial offtakers (e.g. BONDALTI,...)	Providing access to offtaker needs and market entry conditions enables Water Tech developers in the development of products suiting market needs
9. R&D	(non-exhaustive list) Water4All	Access to reference RIs enables applied research at intermediate TRL4-6 levels and increases competitiveness of R&D funding proposals

7.1.5. Benchmarking, assumptions validation, prototyping

A pre-assessment of the KER's competitiveness framework entails a clear vision on its market framework, on its possible advantages towards competing products/services and on its suitability as a solution accepted by its potential market.

To do so, three sets of activities are to be implemented:

- benchmarking: a clear definition of the market addressed by the KER and of the existing competitors/solutions. This benchmarking should define the boundary conditions for the KER competitiveness: which target users; where; for how much;
- assumption validation: a non-biased validation of the assumptions taken in the assessment of the KER's "selling points". Based on available reports and/or inquiries (e.g. "Mom Test"), a non-biased assessment of the existence of the problem (to final users) and on the suitability of the KER as a solution is to be achieved;
- prototyping: used as a tool to validate assumptions or to engage possible exploitation stakeholders (e.g. those defined for the "minimum viable version"), prototyping aims at testing the KER as a suitable solution for addressing the identified problem.

The activity of benchmarking, assumptions validation, and prototyping within Sol2H2O was conceived as a critical step to assess the competitiveness of key exploitable results (KERs) and to ensure their alignment with market expectations. The starting point was a benchmarking exercise that identified the main market frameworks, customer segments, and existing competitors. By analysing reference initiatives and facilities such as Water4All, specialized contract testing laboratories, the consortium was able to establish clear boundary conditions for the future positioning of its solutions. This comparative perspective provided insight into target users, geographical reach, setting a realistic framework for competitive differentiation.

Following this, the activity focused on validating the assumptions underpinning the identified selling points of the KERs. This step involved a systematic approach, making use of market reports, stakeholder consultations, and user-oriented methodologies. The validation process tested not only the existence and relevance of the problems to be solved, but also the willingness of stakeholders to adopt the proposed solutions. By doing so, the consortium reduced the risk of overestimating the market potential and ensured that the solutions being developed were grounded in real and verifiable needs.

Prototyping was then employed as both a technical and strategic tool. The applied case of the INIESC-Évora living lab exemplified this approach. Prototyping activities there included component testing, performance modelling, and integrated system validation, all of which will help to confirm assumptions about the solution's reliability, scalability, and economic viability.

7.1.6. Business Model Generation

As part of the Spin-Off Facility, the activity of *Business Model Generation* was oriented towards translating high-potential research results into concrete and sustainable market opportunities. Building on the resource mapping exercise and the identification of innovation pathways, tailor-made business models were developed to guide the exploitation of results with the strongest potential for commercialization. These models were not conceived in isolation, but rather in close alignment with the overall exploitation strategies of each partner organization, ensuring coherence with institutional missions and long-term strategic goals.

The process followed a structured approach that integrated the stages of ideation, validation, protection, and market entry, as highlighted in the innovation framework presented in Palermo. By addressing value proposition design, competitive advantage, proof of concept, prototyping, usability testing, intellectual property protection, and go-to-market strategies, the activity ensured that each model was comprehensive and adapted to the specific technological outputs under consideration.

An illustrative example of this work was the development of the pitch deck for the potential spin-off *INIESC-Évora*. This applied case demonstrated how a business model can emerge from a research-based initiative and evolve into a structured exploitation plan. The model identified key customer segments (including the metalworking industry, solar concentrator developers, battery manufacturers, and renewable fuel producers) and proposed tailored value propositions for each. It also detailed revenue streams, pricing strategies, and partnership opportunities, while benchmarking the competitive landscape against both direct and indirect competitors (e.g., EU-SOLARIS ERIC, specialized testing providers, technology parks, and incubators).

The exploitation strategy embedded in the business model also included a clear roadmap, moving from capacity building in entrepreneurship and innovation (2024), to business model and plan development (2025), market prospecting (2025–2026), and securing the first clients (2026). This stepwise approach ensures that the exploitation of project results is both realistic and scalable, minimizing risks while maximizing long-term impact.

Ultimately, the *Business Model Generation* activity within Sol2H2O did not only produce theoretical frameworks, but concrete, actionable strategies that can be directly adopted by partners and spin-off initiatives. By combining internal resource mobilization, international best practices, and applied market-driven examples, it laid the foundations for future exploitation plans that can strengthen the project's contribution to sustainable innovation, regional development, and the European Green Transition.

7.1.7. IP and Knowledge Management Strategy

IP and knowledge management strategy will be based on the procedures and agreements included in the Consortium agreement (CA) and Grant Agreement (GA) of the Sol2H2O project.

These documents define the governance framework for managing both background knowledge, meaning the pre-existing expertise and technologies brought by the partners, and foreground knowledge, which consists of the new results generated during the project as identified in the Description of Action (DoA). This structured foundation ensures that ownership, access rights, and exploitation routes are clearly allocated, thereby minimizing potential conflicts and maximizing the value of project outcomes.

In line with the innovation stages highlighted in the Spin-Off Facility, the strategy places strong emphasis on the protection of results before entering the commercialization phase. This includes the consideration of patents, utility models, trademarks, designs, trade secrets, and copyrights as key instruments for securing competitive advantage and enabling future

exploitation. By incorporating these protection mechanisms early in the process, the consortium ensures that promising results are safeguarded against premature disclosure and that they can be strategically leveraged in business models and spin-off initiatives.

Furthermore, the knowledge management component extends beyond legal protection to cover the efficient organization, storage, and sharing of knowledge within the consortium. Tools for documentation management, feedback collection, and collaborative communication identified in the resource mapping exercise are mobilized to ensure transparency and accessibility of information across partners. At the same time, clear procedures for confidentiality and data ownership are enforced, balancing openness in research collaboration with the need to protect commercially sensitive information.

The example of the potential spin-off INIESC-Évora illustrates how IP and knowledge management are integrated into the exploitation pathway. Its business model accounted for the need to protect component testing methods, system performance models, and training know-how, while simultaneously enabling partnerships with industry clients and investors. This demonstrates the dual function of the strategy: safeguarding results to secure long-term competitiveness while also facilitating knowledge transfer to external stakeholders under controlled and mutually beneficial conditions.

7.2. The Exploitation Timeline

The exploitation timeline encompasses the actions starting with the identification of exploitable results and ending with the definition of a Business Plan aiming its exploitation, namely:

- Identification of results: exploitable results identified along the project activities monitoring are identified. This stage has been completed by M30, with the identification of Sol2H2O KER (as described in Section 7.1);
- Evaluation of Business and Innovation Potential: exploitable results identified in the previous step have been analysed from a double business and innovation perspective, bearing in mind the following pillars: Strength of business idea, target sector and competition issues, target market and customers, stakeholders analysis and financial issues. As a result, a single KER with a real potential to become a service has been kept for application of the ensuing steps of the methodology (see Section 7.1);
- Product Standardisation Framework: In view of the future RI support to the exploitation of desalination, brine valorisation and water treatment related products, stemming from Sol2H2O beyond SoA concept, a proper market uptake requires the fulfilment of key regulations, standards and certifications to ensure a smooth commercialisation;
- Exploitation and Business Plan Creation: an updated exploitation plan and a joint business plan are undergoing. Started in M30, this exploitation and joint business plan has already been the base for a joint proposal (see Section 7.3) and is being actively fostered as a post-project activity, aiming at its “embedment” within the business/exploitation plans of each of the Consortium organisations.

The exploitation timeline is illustrated in Table 7.4.

Table 7.4: Sol2H2O exploitation timeline

Exploitation action	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10
Identification of results										
Evaluation of Business and Innovation Potential										
Product Standardisation Framework	N/A						Possible in support of new KER along “beyond SoA”			
Exploitation and Business Plan Creation							Along EU-SOLARIS, SOLARIZE			

Along Project / Post-project

7.3. Exploitation support measures

Aiming at fostering the exploitation of research results by means of the establishment of an exploitation support framework, Sol2H2O included a number of activities gathering the best available expertise and resources in the Consortium.

7.3.1. Spin-off Facility

The Spin-Off Facility within the Sol2H2O project was designed as a comprehensive mechanism to stimulate entrepreneurial capacity and knowledge transfer across its network of partners. Its starting point was a systematic mapping and diagnosis of the available resources that could support the transformation of academic research and technological development into market-ready solutions. This effort led to the creation of a resource matrix, which catalogued and structured the key assets present in the consortium. These included human resources such as product managers, prototype developers, legal advisors, and marketing teams; financial instruments ranging from funding opportunities to investor networks; physical infrastructures like laboratories and offices; specialized tools for prototyping, communication, and project management; and networking opportunities through conferences, incubators, and associations. The matrix thus provided a clear and organized picture of the ecosystem’s capabilities, identifying how each element could be mobilized to accelerate innovation and the creation of spin-offs.

In addition to this internal diagnosis, the Facility also highlighted international success stories and existing networks that demonstrate effective pathways for bridging the so-called “valley of death” between research and commercialization. Examples such as the MIT Energy Initiative, Stanford Climate Ventures, and large-scale collaborations by ETH Zurich and EPFL were presented to show how universities can play a decisive role in supporting the green transition through spin-off creation. These cases illustrated how strategic partnerships, incubation infrastructures, and entrepreneurial education can significantly increase the survival rate and impact of university-based companies, especially in the clean tech sector. By learning from these models, the Sol2H2O consortium positioned its Spin-Off Facility as a platform not only for internal resource mobilization but also for external alignment with global best practices in innovation and entrepreneurship.

To give the initiative a concrete and applied dimension, the Facility showcased a practical example through the development of a pitch deck for a potential spin-off: *INIESC-Évora*. Conceived as a living lab, INIESC-Évora embodies the principles of collaborative innovation by providing real-life testing environments where companies, researchers, and users co-develop,

validate, and optimize renewable energy solutions under operational conditions. The pitch deck outlined the main challenges faced by the sector — including high R&D costs, lack of infrastructure, and the need for component integration — and presented the facility’s value proposition as a response. By offering access to infrastructure, component testing, performance modelling, and technical training, the spin-off would not only accelerate time-to-market for clean water technologies but also reduce costs and risks for its partners. Its business model further identified key customer segments in the water/wastewater treatment industry, brine valorization companies, all of which represent growing markets with strong demand for innovation.

Moreover, the example illustrated how the spin-off could capitalize on competitive advantages such as proximity to local industries, direct collaboration with research institutions, and alignment with EU priorities under the Green Deal. With a staged roadmap including capacity building (2024), business model development (2025), market prospecting (2025–2026), and the acquisition of first clients (2026), INIESC-Évora served as a concrete demonstration of how the Spin-Off Facility could enable sustainable entrepreneurship rooted in the Sol2H2O project’s technological developments.

7.3.2. Project Proposal Facility

Fostering the sustainability of the cooperation initiated with Sol2H2O, the project aims at capitalising the results of both joint research and strategy alignment foreseen in WPs 3-4 into new project proposals.

The preparation of ensuing project proposals not only encompasses the implementation of all relevant research and administrative skills developed along Sol2H2O but also embodies the base for the Cooperation Agreement and Follow-up structure envisaged in WP 1.

This facility will structure and put in place all the required contents of project proposals, namely: (a) a concrete definition of the research approach and expected outcomes; (b) the design of the work plan; (c) a standardised procedure for the description of relevant background; (d) a standardised procedure for the elaboration of project budgeting - aiming at a more efficient call identification / consortium gathering / proposal writing process.

As an outcome of this facility, along Sol2H2O at least one project proposal stemming from the Widening partner is expected for each of the following typologies: (i) Horizon Europe proposal (involving Sol2H2O Consortium); (ii) Portugal 2030 proposal; (iii) Alentejo 2030 proposal; (iv) Industry services proposal.

Additionally, and alongside, the Leading partners will pursue the use of methodologies and resources developed in this facility to the preparation of ensuing national and/or regional funding proposals envisaging the cross-cooperation with the Widening partner (e.g. after the local and/or remote use of its Research Infrastructure).

Table 7.3.2.1: Project proposals in the scope of Sol2H2O

Proposal	Funding	Type	Status (Date)
Seawater as a circular Nature-Based solution for the sustainable management of Water-EnergyFood-Ecosystem Nexus - AQUA MADRE	PRIMA Partnership Topic: 1.1.1-2025 Type of Action: Innovation Action (IA)	International	Awaiting decision - Submitted on the 15th July 2025
Recuperação de sais de salmouras de dessalinização por	Aviso: ALT2030-2024-60	Regional	Awaiting decision - Submitted on the 28th March 2025

Proposal	Funding	Type	Status (Date)
via solar através da integração de reatores de fluxo oscilatório inovadores - RESAL	SACCCT – Projetos de Investigação Científica e Desenvolvimento Tecnológico (IC&DT)		
Recuperação de sais de salmouras de dessalinização solar usando reatores de cristalização inovadores - SaltsDeCry	Aviso n.º MPr-2023-12 - SACCCT - Projetos de IC&DT	Regional	Rejected (05-01-2025)
New circular solutions and decentralized approaches for hospital wastewater management - NEWHO	Call: HORIZON-CL6-2024-CIRCBI O-02 (Circular economy and bioeconomy sectors) Topic: HORIZON-CL6-2024-CircBi o-02-4-two-stage Type of action: HORIZON-IA	European	Rejected (17-05-2024)
New circular and decentralized solutions for sustainable water management in rural areas - AQUA MADRE	Call: HORIZON-CL6-2024-CIRCBI O-02 (Circular economy and bioeconomy sectors) Topic: HORIZON-CL6-2024-CircBi o-02-4-two-stage Type of action: HORIZON-IA	European	Rejected (17-05-2024)

7.3.3. ERC Proposal Facility

In the framework of Sol2H2O, the application to ERC Grants has been sought as an instrument for supporting Young Researchers in the development of a career development plan, aiming at their future leadership of a research team developing activities aligned with the objectives of the Sol2H2O Joint Research Activity (see Deliverable 3.3). Table 7.3.3.1 summarizes the ERC Starting Grant application in the scope of Sol2H2O.

Table 7.3.3.1.: Summary of ERC Starting Grant application by Nunzio Cancilla (UNIPA YR)

Call	
Applicant name	Nunzio Cancilla
Title	Greenhouse Renewable Energy and Environmental Nexus with Water-from-Air Technology for Efficient Resources - GREENWATER
Abstract	The increasing global demand for food and water, along with the urgent need for sustainable agricultural practices, underscores the growing importance of seeking innovative solutions in the management of water resources. The GREENWATER project aims to develop an integrated system that harnesses innovative technologies for harvesting water from the air to generate freshwater for greenhouse irrigation. These technologies will provide an untapped resource for regions facing water scarcity. The harvested water will be used to irrigate crops in a controlled environment, ensuring efficient water use and contributing to sustainable food production. The system will be powered by renewable solar energy sources, enhancing both the overall process sustainability and the agricultural productivity while reducing reliance on fossil fuels. The objective of the GREENWATER project is to optimize the integration between the membrane unit for air-water capture and greenhouse

Call	
	horticulture, with the goal of developing a fully sustainable agricultural model. This will involve the development of a hybrid energy system to ensure a stable energy supply and the implementation of advanced water purification processes, capable of providing water of sufficient quality for crop irrigation. The use of modelling tools such as computational fluid dynamics will be essential to improve the design and performance of the membrane unit, with the objective of increasing the overall efficiency of the water capture process. Additionally, a digital twin system will be developed for performance monitoring, as well as to simulate potential scenarios and operate in real-time, aiming to optimize process performance, reduce energy consumption and maximize yield in both water production and crop output. The research outcomes will have significant implications, particularly for arid and semi-arid regions, where water scarcity and energy consumption pose substantial obstacles to agricultural productivity.
Requested budget	1,496,650.00 €
Assessment	Not selected to proceed to step 2 (rejected).

Regarding a Synergy grant, as the consortium is working with too high TRL levels, it was decided that it was better to reorient the efforts toward higher TRL calls proposals, and a proposal for the PRIMA call was submitted (see Table 7.3.2.1).

7.3.4 Others

UEVORA took part in the 3rd edition of ENERH2O – Energy & Water Innovation & Technology Trade Show, held on September 24–25, 2025, at Exponor, in Porto.

The SALTOpower and Sol2H2O projects, coordinated by the University of Évora, played a prominent role, showcasing cutting-edge work in the field of solar energy for the water-energy nexus and in molten salt technologies for energy applications. This participation proved valuable, as it allowed for the dissemination of the work carried out, the establishment of contacts with companies and professionals in the sector, and the opening of paths for potential future synergies that strengthen the link between research and the market.

Within the conference program, the coordinator of the SOL4R unit, Pedro Horta, delivered a talk dedicated to the topics “Sol2H2O: The potential role of Solar Energy in the Water-Energy Nexus” and “Molten Salt technologies as an Energy Hub for the Energy Transition,” related to both projects, where he also presented the National Research Infrastructure in Concentrated Solar Power (INIESC) and the innovative activities of SOL4R at the Mitra Campus in Évora. He also took part in the session promoted by the Alliance for the Energy Transition, contributing to the debate on green hydrogen and its role in the energy transition.

A proposal for the creation of an Association for Desalination and Wastewater Reuse – Alternative Water Resources (provisional name) has been raised, and was discussed in three meetings: 30th April (Porto), 11th July (Évora) and 23rd September (Porto). These meetings counted with the participation of colleagues from academia and private sector, including small companies and representatives from the Águas de Portugal group. The statutes of the association have been discussed, including the mission, objectives and activities, and a consensus was reached that the innovation and technological developments should be its main focus, as well as networking activities (especially as a way to give the floor to small companies). Further activities include thorough revision of the documents, creation of a list/database of companies and institutions active in these topics, to facilitate the creation of consortia, and the organization of a seminar with presentations aligned with the topics of the association (technological developments for desalination, brine valorisation and wastewater treatment), to be held in January in Porto, and for which other companies from the sector should be invited by current participants.

Further, the development of the ZLD solar desalination Pilot in the framework of the Sol2H2O project served as a basis to enhance the cooperation with the private sector and academia. This cooperation is through the supply of brine produced in the diverse systems of the pilot, to assess alternative crystallization systems, and in the preparation of a proposal in co-promotion to apply for regional funding in the topic of brine valorization, to be submitted by December 2025.

8. LESSONS LEARNED / CONCLUSIONS

The Sol2H2O project defined from the outset an integrated strategy for dissemination, exploitation, and communication to ensure impact across different audiences, supported by a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor implementation. Among the most relevant indicators were the number of participants in scientific and networking events, the number of website visitors and social media followers, as well as newsletter subscribers and media mentions. Graduated success criteria were established to assess the effectiveness of participation in specialized forums, symposia, and training schools, as well as the use of digital platforms for project outreach. Despite the relevance of these indicators, their definition proved to be limited, as they prioritized quantitative metrics such as followers and registrations, rather than the quality of engagement, for example interaction with content, sharing of results, or the actual impact on scientific, institutional, and industrial communities. The evaluation methodology should also have included metrics related to views of key content.

The choice of social media is another critical point. The use of X (formerly Twitter) was not adequate, given its decline in Portugal and Europe, and the nature of the posts did not align with the project's communication needs. Instagram, while popular, also proved misaligned, since it is an image-driven platform, and the project did not "live" from this type of content. Nevertheless, posts with the greatest reach were those that featured project members, often shared in the personal stories of researchers, confirming that humanizing communication generates stronger traction. LinkedIn turned out to be the most suitable network, given its scientific, institutional, and industrial audience. The lesson learned was the need to adapt communication to the formats best suited to the project's profile and target audiences, with initiatives such as "Meet our team" proving more effective.

In terms of dissemination, publishing results in Zenodo by category led to more downloads than initially expected, since the original plan focused mainly on scientific papers. However, if counting only the downloads of scientific publications with the Sol2H2O acknowledgement, the "Excellent" KPI was still achieved. This experience demonstrated that making the presentations available significantly increases visibility and uptake of results.

The Dissemination and Communication KPIs were all achieved, at least at the "Good" level and the "Excellent" several times, which indicates a good effort from the Widening partner with the support of the TOP partners.

Another lesson learned relates to the internal organisation of communication. Since support from the institutional communication department was not available, a dedicated professional was hired to ensure consistency and continuity.

After the conclusion of the project, the website will remain active for at least two years, supporting continued communication through news items, newsletters, and RSS feeds. Public deliverables will be published on Zenodo, the website, and social media, and open-access papers will also be made available.

In summary, the project succeeded in designing a robust dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategy, but the experience demonstrated that engagement depends less on the sheer number of followers or events organized, and more on the alignment between channels, content, and audiences. The main conclusion is that future initiatives should focus on

personalized content, highlighting the people behind the work and the real impact of results, measured not only by outreach numbers but also by downloads, citations, and the development of new scientific and technological initiatives—thereby ensuring the long-term legacy of the project beyond its official end.

9. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedule and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Data Management Plan

The *Data Management Plan* describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated in a project. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan

The *Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan* describes the DEC activities foreseen for the project. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive located on the DLR server in Germany. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. The Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. The Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, the Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available, and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive, and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A and B) <Grant Agreement-101079305-Sol2H2O>	Project folder
3	Deliverables acceptance plan <[08.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Plan. SOL2H2O.16-02-2023.v.1>	Project Folder
4	Deliverables acceptance Checklist <[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Chec klist.SOL2H2O.16-02-2023.v1.0>	Project Folder
5	Data Management Plan <SOL2H2O_D_1_2_DATA_MANAGEMENT_PLA N>	Project Folder
6	Scope and Success Criteria <SOL2H2O_Scope and Success Criteria_v1>	Project Folder
7	Social networks, Newsletter, Website, and Scientific Publications <SOL2H2O_Social networks, Newsletter, Website, and Scientific Publications>	Project Folder
8	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan <SOL2H2O_D_1_3_DEC_PLAN>	Project Folder

APPENDIX 2: SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Scientific Publication	DOI	Link in Zenodo	Sol2H2O Acknowledgement
Influence of internal design on the performance of pilot vacuum-assisted airgap membrane distillation modules for brine concentration with solar energy I. Requena, J.A. Andrés-Mañas, G. Zaragoza	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10777185	https://zenodo.org/records/10777185	Yes
Design of a high-recovery zero-liquid discharge solar desalination pilot: aiming a beyond state-of-the-art concept, Euromed/EDS 2024 F. Felizardo, P. Horta, A. Cipollina, N. Cancilla, G. Zaragoza, I. Requena, J. Antonio de la Fuente, Á. Rivero-Falcón	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12733055	https://zenodo.org/records/12733055	Yes
Performance evaluation of nanofiltration membranes for SWRO brine valorisation: Insights from a pilot plant under real conditions, Separation and Purification Technology 2025 A. Rivero-Falcón, Y. López-López, B. Peñate Suárez, N. Melián-Martel	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2024.130774	https://zenodo.org/records/14608283	No
Influence of thermal buoyancy on heat transfer in spacer-filled channels for Membrane Distillation, UIT 2024 M. Ciofalo, N. Cancilla, A. Cipollina, A. Tamburini, G. Micale	https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2940/1/012007	https://zenodo.org/records/14793209	Yes
The Operational Performance of an Ultrafiltration Pilot Unit for the Treatment of Ultra-Concentrated Brines, G. Scelfo, P. Serrano-Tari, R. Raffaelli, F. Vicari, I. Oller, A. Cipollina, A. Tamburini, G. Micale	https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes14120276	https://zenodo.org/records/15622435	Yes
Innovative testbed for desalination brine valorisation: circular economy and NF-OARO synergies from Desal+ Living Lab, EDS 2025 A. Rivero Falcón, Y. López López, B. Peñate Suárez, N. Melián Martel	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15622611	https://zenodo.org/records/15622611	Yes
Commissioning a solar-powered zero liquid discharge desalination pilot: Sol2H2O joint research, EDS 2025 F. Felizardo, P. Horta, A. Cipollina, N. Cancilla, G.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15622811	https://zenodo.org/records/15622811	Yes

Scientific Publication	DOI	Link in Zenodo	Sol2H2O Acknowledgement
Zaragoza, I. Requena, J. Antonio de la Fuente, Á. Rivero-Falcón			
Application of Machine Learning to Characterize the Permeate Quality in Pilot-Scale Vacuum-Assisted Air Gap Membrane Distillation Operation I. Requena, J. Antonio Andrés-Mañas, J. Diego Gil, G. Zaragoza	https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes13110857	https://zenodo.org/records/15878403	No
Optimización de las etapas de pretratamiento (NF) y concentración (OARO) como procesos clave para la adecuada valorización de salmueras AEDyR 2025 A. Rivero-Falcón, Y. López-López, B. Peñate Suárez	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17225979	https://zenodo.org/records/17225979	Yes

APPENDIX 3: ENERGY STRATEGY SYMPOSIUM

Communication and dissemination made before, after and during the Water-Energy Strategy Symposium, held in Évora.

Exmos. Senhores e Senhoras,

no âmbito do projeto **Twinning HEUROPE Sol2H2O**, coordenado pela **Universidade de Évora** e com a participação do Centro de Investigações Medioambientais de Espanha (**CIEMAT**), da Universidade de Palermo (**UNIPA**) e do Instituto Tecnológico das Canárias (**ITC**), na sequência dos Fóruns de Especialização Regional, vamos organizar o **simpósio nacional Water-Energy Strategy**, focado na discussão com atores regionais e nacionais de diferentes soluções tecnológicas para a produção e tratamento de águas por via solar (nomeadamente, dessalinização e fotocatalise solares). O WESSymp visa ainda a apresentação e discussão do papel potencial das tecnologias Água-Energia nos objectivos do Plano Nacional de Energia e Clima, bem como do potencial de desenvolvimento industrial e exportação de tecnologia decorrente da aplicação da capacidade industrial existente/em desenvolvimento às soluções tecnológicas procuradas no Sol2H2O.

Temos o gosto de os convidar a participar neste simpósio que irá decorrer em Évora (evento presencial, com visita à infraestrutura de investigação), no dia **6 de Fevereiro de 2025** --> [SAVE THE DATE](#)

Brevemente, disponibilizaremos a agenda e formulário de inscrição.

Esperamos contar com a vossa presença,
votos de Boas Festas!

A coordenação Sol2H2O

Sugerimos a consulta do site Sol2H2O (<https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/>), das redes sociais do projeto (<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/sol2h2o>, <https://www.instagram.com/sol2h2o/> e <https://twitter.com/Sol2H2OHEUROPE>) e a subscrição da newsletter (<https://uevora.us21.list-manage.com/subscribe?u=82203fd65b9dc598eaca0d06a0&id=5a59276acb>).

Save the date email sent before the symposium

Water-Energy Strategy Symposium

15/01/2025

The event will take place on February 6th in Évora

As part of the Twinning HEUROPE Sol2H2O project, coordinated by the University of Évora, and with the participation of the Spanish Center for Environmental Research (CIEMAT), the University of Palermo (UNIPA), and the Canary Islands Technological Institute (ITC), we would like to invite you to participate in the National Symposium on **Water-Energy Strategy**, to be held on February 6, 2025, at the University of Évora.

This symposium focuses on discussions with regional and national stakeholders regarding the role of the Water-Energy nexus in achieving the objectives of the National Energy and Climate Plan, as well as the industrial development potential of various technological solutions for water production and treatment using solar energy.

The event will take place at Casa Cordovil in Évora. Confirm your attendance [here](#) by January 30th.

Website publication¹⁴ before the symposium

¹⁴ <https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/water-energy-strategy-symposium/>

Hello!

We are delighted to invite you to participate in the **National Symposium on Water-Energy Strategy**, which will take place on **February 6 in Évora, Portugal**.

This event will bring together experts, researchers, industry leaders, and policymakers to discuss the challenges and opportunities of integrated water and energy management — crucial topics for a sustainable future.

The event will be in Portuguese.

Water-Energy Strategy

Special invitation newsletter for the symposium¹⁵

¹⁵ <https://mailchi.mp/c58bcd07b4fe/sol2h2o-newsletter-12715298>

Projeto Europeu Sol2H2O organiza simpósio nacional sobre Água e Energia em Évora

Évora, 21 de janeiro de 2025 – A Cátedra de Energias Renováveis da Universidade de Évora, organiza no próximo dia 6 de fevereiro o simpósio nacional "Water-Energy Strategy", um evento do projeto europeu Sol2H2O.

O evento reúne atores regionais e nacionais para discutir o papel estratégico do nexo Água-Energia no cumprimento dos objetivos do Plano Nacional de Energia e Clima (PNEC), bem como as oportunidades de desenvolvimento industrial em tecnologias solares para produção e tratamento de água.

O simpósio, que faz parte do projeto Twinning HEUROPE Sol2H2O, conta com a participação de parceiros internacionais, como o Centro de Investigações Medioambientais de Espanha (CIEMAT), a Universidade de Palermo (UNIPA) e o Instituto Tecnológico das Canárias (ITC).

As atividades terão início às 09h30, nas instalações da Cátedra de Energias Renováveis da Universidade de Évora, localizadas na Herdade da Mitra, com sessões de debate a decorrer na Casa Cordovil, no centro histórico de Évora.

Informações sobre o Evento

Data: 6 de fevereiro de 2025

Hora: A partir das 09h30

Local: Cátedra de Energias Renováveis, Universidade de Évora, Herdade da Mitra

Press release sent before the symposium

Simpósio “Water-Energy Strategy” debate desafios e soluções para o futuro da água em Portugal

O simpósio “Water-Energy Strategy” dedicado aos desafios e possíveis soluções para o futuro da água em Portugal, organizado pela Cátedra de Energias Renováveis da Universidade de Évora, decorreu no passado dia 6 de Fevereiro, no âmbito do projeto Sol2H2O e foi um sucesso, contando com a presença de diversas entidades e especialistas do setor.

Durante o dia, foram debatidos desafios e oportunidades para a gestão sustentável dos recursos hídricos, resultando em diversas ideias para um futuro mais resiliente e eficiente.

Marcaram presença entidades de renome, como a Administração da Região Hidrográfica do Alentejo, a Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços de Águas e Resíduos, a EPAL - Empresa Portuguesa das Águas Livres, o Departamento de Hydraulics & Water Resources Resilience da EDP e a Água e Resíduos da Madeira.

O simpósio culminou numa mesa redonda sob o tema Nexo Água-Energia: integração de energias renováveis na produção e tratamento de água, que contou com João Crespo (Universidade Nova de Lisboa), Carina Arranja (Federação Nacional de Regantes) e Sandra Jorge (Águas do Centro Litoral), especialistas que partilharam experiências, desafios e soluções para a gestão eficiente da água no país.

Ao longo do evento, foram discutidos temas essenciais como a sustentabilidade hídrica, a inovação tecnológica no setor e a adaptação às alterações climáticas. O debate proporcionou um espaço para reflexão e colaboração entre diferentes agentes do setor, reforçando a importância de uma estratégia nacional integrada para a gestão da água e a oportunidade de, à semelhança do que sucede em Espanha ou Itália - países parceiros do projecto Sol2H2O - se iniciar uma discussão quanto à criação de uma associação nacional para a dessalinização e reutilização de águas residuais.

O evento reafirmou a necessidade de colaboração contínua entre entidades públicas, privadas e académicas, garantindo que o futuro da água no país seja marcado por inovação, resiliência e sustentabilidade.

Press release sent after the symposium

Instagram¹⁶ with publications before and after the symposium (the same were made on LinkedIn)

¹⁶ <https://www.instagram.com/sol2h2o/>
<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/sol2h2o/>

Symposium “Water-Energy Strategy” discusses challenges and solutions for the future of water in Portugal

11/02/2025

The event was a great success, bringing together various entities and experts from the sector

The symposium “Water-Energy Strategy”, dedicated to the challenges and possible solutions for the future of water in Portugal, was organized by the Renewable Energies Chair of the University of Évora on February 6, as part of the Sol2H2O project. The event was a great success, bringing together various entities and experts from the sector.

Throughout the day, participants discussed challenges and opportunities for the sustainable management of water resources, resulting in several ideas for a more resilient and efficient future.

Renowned entities attended the event, including the Alentejo Regional Hydrographic Administration, the Regulatory Authority for Water and Waste Services, EPAL – Empresa Portuguesa das Águas Livres, the Hydraulics & Water Resources Resilience Department of EDP, and Água e Resíduos da Madeira.

Website publication¹⁷ after the symposium

17

<https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt/symposium-water-energy-strategy-discusses-challenges-and-solutions-for-the-future-of-water-in-portugal/>

APPENDIX 4: SOCIAL MEDIA

- X - Number of followers decreasing

Date	LinkedIn	Twitter - X
M1 - dec 2022		
M2		
M3 - feb 2023	0	0
M4	17	
M5	21	
M6	22	
M7	25	
M8	27	
M9	32	
M10 - sep 2023	32	3
M11	37	4
M12	48	7
M13	58	7
M14	78	
M15 - feb 2024	96	40
M16	132	53
M17	168	56
M18	191	61
M19	202	69
M20 - jul2024	206	58
M21	210	67
M22	216	60
M23	219	59
M24	222	25
M25	223	10
M26	230	10
M27	235	0
M28	236	0
M29	239	0
M30 - may 2025	241	0
M31	245	0
M32	248	0
M33	247	0
M34		
M35		
M36 - nov 2025		

- LinkedIn

European Training for research in Solar energy to (2) water (H2O) production and treatment technologies
 GA Number: 101070305
 European Research Executive Agency REACT3

Financed by the European Union

Sol2H2O

Sol2H2O
 Solar Water - Energy Nexus
 Pesquisa e desenvolvimento científico · Évora · 247 seguidores

 João e mais 93 conexões seguem esta página

✉ Envie mensagem
✓ Seguindo
⋮

[Início](#) [Sobre](#) [Publicações](#)

Visão geral

By means of enhanced cooperation duly framed on a common research strategy aiming at further developing Solar-driven Water-Energy Nexus solutions, Sol2H2O aims at creating a reference European facility for the development and testing of Circular Solar-driven Water Production & Treatment t ... ver mais

Sol2H2O
247 seguidores
3 sem · 🌐

"A descarbonização e a utilização de recursos hídricos alternativos"

Artigo por Pedro Horta, coordenador do SOL4R e do projeto Sol2H2O, na ...mais

Aspectos N212
calameo.com

👤 1

👤 Gostei 💬 Comentar ➦ Compartilhar ➦ Enviar

Sol2H2O
247 seguidores
1 m · 🌐

Sol2H2O Italian Symposium: Advancing Desalination Technologies for a Sustainable Future ...mais

Exibir tradução

Sol2H2O Italian Symposium: Advancing Desalination Technologies for a Sustainable Future
sol2h2o.uevora.pt

👤 1

👤 Gostei 💬 Comentar ➦ Compartilhar ➦ Enviar

Sol2H2O
247 seguidores
1 m · 🌐

UNIPA candidate young researchers in Évora

Between May 5th and 16th, 2025, the University of Évora hosted a technical ...mais

Exibir tradução

UNIPA candidate young researchers in Évora
sol2h2o.uevora.pt

👤 11 1 compartilhamento

👤 Gostei 💬 Comentar ➦ Compartilhar ➦ Enviar

Sol2H2O
247 seguidores
2 m · 🌐

★ Sol2H2O: European Twinning for research in Solar energy to water production & treatment technologies ...mais

Exibir tradução

Sol2H2O: European Twinning for research in Solar energy to water production & treatment technologies
youtube.com

👤 1 1 compartilhamento

Sol2H2O compartilhou isso

itc Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias
26.539 seguidores
11 m · 🌐

🟢 Esta semana acogemos en #GranCanaria la reunión de seguimiento del proyecto Sol2H2O, con presencia de todos sus socios procedentes de Portugal, Italia y España. ...mais

Exibir tradução

👤 44 4 compartilhamentos

👤 Gostei 💬 Comentar ➦ Compartilhar ➦ Enviar

● **YouTube**

 Renewable Energies Chair
@RenewableEnergiesChair · 17 subscribers · 22 videos

The RE Chair aims at developing technological solutions and Solar energy applications for ...more
[catedraer.uevora.pt](#) and 1 more link

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Created playlists

Sol2H2O
Consortium and Project Objectives
11 videos

Sol2H2O
View full playlist

SALTOpower
13 videos

SALTOpower
View full playlist

Sol2H2O
Renewable Energies Chair - 1/11

↻ ↺ ⋮

- Sol2H2O Consortium and Project Objectives - Sol2H2O FTS#1 - ...**
Renewable Energies Chair
18:44
- Intro to Sustainable Desalination Strategies - ...**
Renewable Energies Chair
31:21
- Sol2H2O State of the Art of Membrane Distillation - Sol2H2O FTS#1 - ...**
Renewable Energies Chair
24:28
- Sol2H2O Solar water treatment, integration of tech for WW...**
Renewable Energies Chair
23:33
- State of the art of SWRO desalination brine valorizatio...**
Renewable Energies Chair
26:03
- State of the art of PV-RO - Sol2H2O FTS#1 - Toni de la...**
Renewable Energies Chair
39:40
- State of the art of Brine treatment - Sol2H2O FTS#1 - ...**
Renewable Energies Chair
31:38
- Sol2H2O MF-PFR for selective recovery of Mg and Ca from brines - ...**
Renewable Energies Chair
39:00
- Sol2H2O Fast Track School #2**

● **Instagram**

sol2h2o ▾ ● 🌐 + ☰

Sol2H2O HEUROPE Twinning
90 publicações 75 seguidores 55 a seguir

Solar Water - Energy Nexus
🔗 youtu.be/tGojcJZHw3c?si=3_4NvWvC4CIMgQ...
Universidade de Évora, Évora

Painel Profissional
➤ mil visualizações nos últimos 30 dias.

Editar perfil Partilhar per... Contacto

Novo ProM#5 & FT... ProM #4 & FT...

APPENDIX 5: NEWSLETTER

- Newsletter #1 - <https://mailchi.mp/50ba2051cf36/sol2h2o-newsletter-1>
- Newsletter #2 - <https://mailchi.mp/612a9ae47b75/sol2h2o-newsletter-12660247>
- Newsletter #3 - <https://mailchi.mp/54a89c46a2a7/sol2h2o-newsletter-12676266>
- Newsletter #4 - <https://mailchi.mp/d8a1fcc0c236/sol2h2o-newsletter-12690466>
- Newsletter #5 - <https://mailchi.mp/d260774d457c/sol2h2o-newsletter-12693928>
- Newsletter #6 - <https://mailchi.mp/493a8bd492c2/sol2h2o-newsletter-12695885>
- Newsletter #7 - <https://mailchi.mp/250742530d94/sol2h2o-newsletter-12706994>
- Newsletter #8 - <https://mailchi.mp/67f3586d706e/sol2h2o-newsletter-12713338>
- Newsletter “Water-Energy Strategy” Symposium -
<https://mailchi.mp/c58bcd07b4fe/sol2h2o-newsletter-12715298>
- Newsletter #9 - <https://mailchi.mp/f037cc28050c/sol2h2o-newsletter-12718887>
- Newsletter #10 - <https://mailchi.mp/4da7d1ffe3df/sol2h2o-newsletter-12745967>
- Newsletter #11 - <https://mailchi.mp/f8dcd63de39d/sol2h2o-newsletter-12747021>
- Newsletter #12 - <https://mailchi.mp/787bfc34a734/sol2h2o-newsletter-12747070>

APPENDIX 6: PRESS RELEASES

Projeto Europeu Sol2H2O organiza simpósio nacional sobre Água e Energia em Évora

Évora, 21 de janeiro de 2025 – A Cátedra de Energias Renováveis da Universidade de Évora, organiza no próximo dia 6 de fevereiro o simpósio nacional “Water-Energy Strategy”, um evento do projeto europeu Sol2H2O.

O evento reúne atores regionais e nacionais para discutir o papel estratégico do nexo Água-Energia no cumprimento dos objetivos do Plano Nacional de Energia e Clima (PNEC), bem como as oportunidades de desenvolvimento industrial em tecnologias solares para produção e tratamento de água.

O simpósio, que faz parte do projeto Twinning HEUROPE Sol2H2O, conta com a participação de parceiros internacionais, como o Centro de Investigações Medioambientais de Espanha (CIEMAT), a Universidade de Palermo (UNIPA) e o Instituto Tecnológico das Canárias (ITC).

As atividades terão início às 09h30, nas instalações da Cátedra de Energias Renováveis da Universidade de Évora, localizadas na Herdade da Mitra, com sessões de debate a decorrer na Casa Cordovil, no centro histórico de Évora.

Informações sobre o Evento

Data: 6 de fevereiro de 2025

Hora: A partir das 09h30

Local: Cátedra de Energias Renováveis, Universidade de Évora, Herdade da Mitra

Media publications:

- <https://diariosul.pt/2025/01/27/projeto-europeu-sol2h2o-organiza-simposio-nacional-sobre-agua-e-energia-em-evora/>
- <https://regiao-sul.pt/ambiente/sol2h2o-organiza-simposio-nacional-sobre-agua-e-energia-em-evora/698267>
- https://radionovaantena.com/2025/01/25/projeto-europeu-sol2h2o-organiza-simposio-nacional-sobre-agua-e-energia-em-evora/#google_vignette
- https://odigital.sapo.pt/universidade-de-evora-promove-simposio-nacional-sobre-agua-e-energia/?no_cache=1&fbclid=IwY2xjawlEdaFleHRuA2FibQIxMQABHV1N9AuzBq_s-fYsmjEUPlwjDtaF7UqUbj3XqcGjqSAzMnNmpdmtfPYQ_aem_t_PvB6WgldDDWZfVsBtSfw
- <https://adefesa.org/2025/01/29/jornal-a-defesa-29-de-janeiro-de-2025-edicao-digital/>

Simpósio “Water-Energy Strategy” debate desafios e soluções para o futuro da água em Portugal

O simpósio “Water-Energy Strategy” dedicado aos desafios e possíveis soluções para o futuro da água em Portugal, organizado pela Cátedra de Energias Renováveis da Universidade de Évora, decorreu no passado dia 6 de Fevereiro, no âmbito do projeto Sol2H2O e foi um sucesso, contando com a presença de diversas entidades e especialistas do setor.

Durante o dia, foram debatidos desafios e oportunidades para a gestão sustentável dos recursos hídricos, resultando em diversas ideias para um futuro mais resiliente e eficiente.

Marcaram presença entidades de renome, como a Administração da Região Hidrográfica do Alentejo, a Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços de Águas e Resíduos, a EPAL - Empresa Portuguesa das Águas Livres, o Departamento de Hydraulics & Water Resources Resilience da EDP e a Água e Resíduos da Madeira.

O simpósio culminou numa mesa redonda sob o tema Nexo Água-Energia: integração de energias renováveis na produção e tratamento de água, que contou com João Crespo (Universidade Nova de Lisboa), Carina Arranja (Federação Nacional de Regantes) e Sandra Jorge (Águas do Centro Litoral), especialistas que partilharam experiências, desafios e soluções para a gestão eficiente da água no país.

Ao longo do evento, foram discutidos temas essenciais como a sustentabilidade hídrica, a inovação tecnológica no setor e a adaptação às alterações climáticas. O debate proporcionou um espaço para reflexão e colaboração entre diferentes agentes do setor, reforçando a importância de uma estratégia nacional integrada para a gestão da água e a oportunidade de, à semelhança do que sucede em Espanha ou Itália - países parceiros do projecto Sol2H2O - se iniciar uma discussão quanto à criação de uma associação nacional para a dessalinização e reutilização de águas residuais.

O evento reafirmou a necessidade de colaboração contínua entre entidades públicas, privadas e académicas, garantindo que o futuro da água no país seja marcado por inovação, resiliência e sustentabilidade.

Media publications:

- <https://www.agroportal.pt/simposio-water-energy-strategy-debate-desafios-e-solucoes-para-o-futuro-do-tratamento-da-agua-em-portugal/>
- <https://diariodosul.pt/2025/02/11/evora-simposio-water-energy-strategy-debate-desafios-e-solucoes-para-o-futuro-do-tratamento-da-agua-em-portugal/>
- https://radionovaantena.com/2025/02/11/simposio-water-energy-strategy-debate-desafios-e-solucoes-para-o-futuro-dotratamento-da-agua-em-portugal/#google_vignette
- <https://jornalaltoalentejo.sapo.pt/evora-simposio-water-energy-strategy-debate-desafios-e-solucoes-para-o-futuro-do-tratamento-da-agua-em-portugal/>

Simpósio Internacional "Water-Energy Transition" dedicado à transição energética no setor da Água

O simpósio internacional "Water-Energy Strategy" dedicado ao nexo Água-Energia, especificamente à transição energética no setor da Água, decorreu em formato online no passado mês de julho.

Organizado no âmbito do projeto europeu [Sol2H2O](#), pela Cátedra de Energias Renováveis da Universidade de Evora em colaboração com os parceiros do consórcio, Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT, Espanha), Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias (ITC, Espanha), e a Universidade de Palermo (UNIPA, Itália), foi o culminar de diversos eventos nacionais realizados em Portugal, Espanha e Itália.

A participação no evento foi expressiva, com mais de 40 participantes provenientes de entidades públicas e privadas, incluindo diversas empresas do setor, que tiveram oportunidade de apresentar projetos de inovação tecnológica no tratamento de águas residuais, produção de água por via de dessalinização e valorização de saimouras de dessalinização.

Durante o evento foram apresentados os resultados das sessões nacionais, durante as quais se utilizou a metodologia de brainstorming 6-3-5 para responder a cinco questões previamente definidas. Estas incidiram sobre os desafios e potenciais soluções para a implementação de processos de tratamento de água para produção de Água para Reutilização (ApR), nomeadamente na irrigação; a implementação com sucesso de soluções de descarga Zero Líquida (ZLD) no mercado; o armazenamento de água enquanto solução para o armazenamento de energia no caso de sistemas de energia renovável em larga escala.

Estas sessões nacionais permitiram a identificação de desafios e soluções comuns entre Portugal, Espanha e Itália, enfatizando a sua transversalidade.

No que respeita à produção de ApR, destacaram-se questões económicas relacionadas com o custo da tecnologia, sociais relacionadas com a perceção do risco de utilização da ApR por parte das populações e agricultores, e barreiras administrativas e regulatórias. Como solução, foi sugerida a melhoria da comunicação e a revisão do enquadramento legal (com envolvimento dos stakeholders).

Sobre as soluções ZLD foram abordadas questões relacionadas com a sua viabilidade económica a larga escala, com foco nas necessidades energéticas e na consciencialização da saimoura enquanto recurso, sendo sugerido o investimento em I&D, o incentivo à economia circular e à realização de estudos de mercado para os produtos recuperados da saimoura.

Adicionalmente, destacou-se a relevância da gestão da água como elemento na gestão da energia elétrica, incluindo, a sua produção, armazenamento geo-estratégico e distribuição.

A discussão, moderada pelo coordenador do projeto Sol2H2O, Doutor Pedro Horta, foi bastante participada, revelando o interesse e conhecimento dos participantes sobre estas temáticas. Foram identificadas barreiras e apresentadas sugestões relacionadas com a otimização dos processos de dessalinização e do design das plantas de dessalinização, incluindo a integração de fontes de energia renovável e processos de valorização das saimouras; a necessidade de estudos económicos detalhados para avaliar a potencial implementação das tecnologias de valorização de saimouras no mercado; e as necessidades de implementação de uma rede de distribuição da ApR, permitindo uma reutilização de águas residuais tratadas mais efetiva, assim como da disseminação mais eficaz de resultados de I&D relacionados com a qualidade da ApR para irrigação.

O evento reafirmou a importância da colaboração contínua entre entidades públicas, privadas e académicas, garantindo que a gestão do nexo Água-Energia na Europa seja marcada por inovação, resiliência e sustentabilidade.

Media publications:

- <https://www.agroportal.pt/simposio-internacional-debate-nexo-agua-energia/>
- <https://odigital.sapo.pt/mais-de-40-entidades-reunidas-em-simposio-internacional-sobre-agua-e-energia-organizado-pela-universidade-de-evora/>
- <https://diariodosul.pt/2025/08/27/simposio-internacional-water-energy-transition-dedicado-a-transicao-energetica-no-setor-da-agua/>

Projetos da Cátedra de Energias Renováveis da UÉvora marcam presença na feira internacional ENERH2O

Nos dias 24 e 25 de setembro de 2025, a Cátedra de Energias Renováveis da Universidade de Évora (CER-UÉ) estará presente na 3ª edição da ENERH2O – Energy & Water Innovation & Technology Trade Show, na Exponor, Porto.

Este é um dos principais eventos profissionais dedicados à inovação nos setores da energia e da gestão da água. O encontro reúne empresas, instituições, investigadores e startups para debater soluções tecnológicas e apresentar projetos que respondem aos grandes desafios da transição energética e da sustentabilidade.

A CER-UÉ irá marcar presença com os projetos Twinning, SALTOpower e Sol2H2O, ambos Horizonte Europa. Os Twinning terão um papel de destaque numa das conferências do evento, denominada: "Apresentação dos projetos europeus Sol2H2O and SALTOpower: Technology, research, and value chain". Estes projetos assumem-se como exemplos de como a ciência e a tecnologia podem apoiar a competitividade das empresas e contribuir para uma matriz energética mais sustentável.

A ENERH2O contará ainda com uma conferência promovida pela Aliança para a Transição Energética (ATE), que reunirá especialistas para debater os caminhos da transição energética em Portugal. Um dos convidados será o Dr. Pedro Horta, coordenador da unidade SOL4R.

Com um programa diversificado, a ENERH2O afirma-se como um espaço privilegiado de encontro entre academia, indústria e entidades públicas, promovendo networking, transferência de conhecimento e parcerias estratégicas. A participação da CER-UÉ e dos seus projetos sublinha o papel da investigação científica na construção de soluções inovadoras para os desafios energéticos e ambientais que marcam o presente e moldam o futuro.

Media publications:

- <https://www.rederural.gov.pt/pt/projetos-relevantes?view=article&id=8511:universidad-e-de-evora-leva-inovacao-energetica-e-hidrica-a-feira-enerh2o-no-porto&catid=12>
- https://odigital.sapo.pt/projetos-da-universidade-de-evora-em-destaque-na-feira-internacional-enerh2o/#google_vignette

Fast-Track Schools dos projetos [SALTOpower](#) e Sol2H2O capacitam jovens investigadores em armazenamento de energia e exploração de recursos hídricos alternativos

Os projetos europeus Twinning, [SALTOpower](#) e Sol2H2O, financiados pelo programa Horizonte Europa, concluíram os seus ciclos de Fast-Track Schools dedicados à capacitação de jovens investigadores, doutorandos e especialistas da indústria em áreas fundamentais para a transição energética e a gestão sustentável da água.

Enquanto o [SALTOpower](#) evidencia o potencial dos sais fundidos para o armazenamento térmico de energia e para a integração de energias renováveis em setores emergentes como o calor de processo industrial ou as baterias térmicas tipo Carnot, o Sol2H2O coloca o foco em soluções solares para dessalinização, tratamento de águas residuais e recuperação de recursos a partir de salmouras, oferecendo respostas inovadoras para a segurança hídrica em regiões vulneráveis.

No âmbito do [SALTOpower](#), as formações decorreram em Itália, Alemanha e Portugal e exploraram o papel das tecnologias de sais fundidos no armazenamento de energia e na integração de renováveis no sistema energético, abordando não apenas os fundamentos científicos destas tecnologias mas também a sua aplicação e potencial de mercado.

No âmbito do Sol2H2O, as Fast-Track Schools foram realizadas em Itália, Espanha e Portugal, centrando-se em tecnologias solares para produção e tratamento de água e em processos de valorização de salmouras, combinando conteúdos de investigação básica, implementação experimental e benchmarking tecnológico com oportunidades de exploração de mercado.

No total, as diferentes edições registaram mais de uma centena de inscrições e a participação ativa de jovens investigadores de várias nacionalidades, tanto em formato presencial como online. Com uma elevada taxa de satisfação (superior a 4 em 5 pontos), confirmando a relevância dos temas abordados e a qualidade dos materiais distribuídos, a formação inclui, para além das sessões técnicas, visitas a infraestruturas de referência e trabalho colaborativo e de brainstorming, nos quais os jovens investigadores tiveram um papel central na definição de planos de investigação e no debate sobre os desafios atuais nos domínios da energia e do nexo água-energia.

Todos os materiais das Fast-Track Schools, incluindo apresentações e gravações, estão disponíveis online nos websites dos projetos.

[Website SALTOpower](#)

[Website Sol2H2O](#)

Media publications:

- <https://odigital.sapo.pt/evora-jovens-investigadores-capacitados-em-energias-renovaveis-e-solucoes-solares-para-a-agua/>

- **After ENERH2O - Trade Show press release and media publications links**

SOL4R e INIESC levam inovação em energias renováveis à ENERH2O 2025

A SOL4R Applied Research in Solar Energy for the Energy Transition (FCT UID 6478) marcou presença na 3ª edição da ENERH2O – Energy & Water Innovation & Technology Trade Show, que decorreu nos dias 24 e 25 de setembro de 2025 na Exponor, no Porto.

Os projetos SALTOpower e Sol2H2O, coordenados pela Universidade de Évora, tiveram um papel de destaque, mostrando o que de melhor se faz no âmbito da energia solar para o nexu água-energia e nas tecnologias de sais fundidos para aplicações energéticas. Esta participação revelou-se uma mais-valia, pois permitiu divulgar o trabalho desenvolvido, estabelecer contactos com empresas e profissionais do setor e abrir caminho a possíveis sinergias futuras que reforçam a ligação entre investigação e mercado.

No quadro das conferências do certame, o coordenador da unidade SOL4R, Pedro Horta, apresentou uma conferência dedicada às temáticas “Sol2H2O: The potential role of Solar Energy in the Water-Energy Nexus” e “Molten Salt technologies as an Energy Hub for the Energy Transition”, relacionadas com ambos os projetos, na qual foi apresentada a Infraestrutura Nacional de Investigação em Energia Solar de Concentração (INIESC) e as atividades inovadoras da SOL4R no Pólo da Mitra em Évora. Participou também na sessão promovida pela Aliança para a Transição Energética, contribuindo para o debate sobre o hidrogénio verde e o seu papel na transição energética.

Com esta presença, a SOL4R e a INIESC consolidaram a sua posição no panorama nacional de investigação em energia solar, reforçando o seu compromisso com o desenvolvimento de soluções tecnológicas sustentáveis.

O evento reuniu cerca de uma centena de empresas dos setores energético e da água de Portugal e Espanha e contou com cerca de 40 conferências dedicadas à inovação nos domínios da energia e da água.

Media publications:

- <https://www.agroportal.pt/ue-leva-inovacao-a-enerh2o/>

Horizon Europe
Sol2H2O
GA no. 101079906

Università
degli Studi
di Palermo

Centro di
Sostenibilità
e Transizione
Ecologica

COMUNICATO STAMPA

Primo Simposio Nazionale “La Dissalazione dell'acqua di mare e le tecnologie correlate nel contesto del Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem (WEFE) Nexus”

Nelle giornate dell'1 e 2 luglio, si è svolto a Palermo, presso il Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell'Università del capoluogo siciliano, il Primo Simposio Nazionale in materia di dissalazione e della importanza della sinergia tra i sistemi idrici, energetici ed alimentare.

L'evento, organizzato da UNIPA, AIDARA e dall'Ordine degli Ingegneri di Palermo, ha rappresentato un momento di grande importanza per fornire una chiara panoramica dell'emergenza idrica in corso e delle soluzioni adottate, sia con l'approccio di urgenza, sia con la prospettiva di medio periodo.

Il Simposio fa parte delle attività di ricerca svolte dall'Università degli Studi di Palermo nell'ambito del progetto Horizon Europe Sol2H2O (<https://www.sol2h2o.uevora.pt>), che vede la partecipazione di partner internazionali come l'Universidade de Évora (UEvora) in Portogallo, il Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT) e l'Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias (ITC), queste ultime entrambe in Spagna.

Si sono succeduti 5 panels, che hanno rappresentato l'importanza della dissalazione, quale uno degli strumenti fondamentali per assicurare risorsa idrica continua e potabile alle comunità locali ed agli operatori economici, sia da punto di vista delle Autorità pubbliche nazionali e locali competenti, da quello dei gestori e distributori della risorsa, da quello degli operatori che sviluppano e forniscono tecnologie, sistemi, impianti, processi.

Grazie alla partecipazione del Commissario straordinario nazionale, presso la Presidenza del Consiglio dei Ministri, per l'adozione di interventi urgenti connessi al fenomeno della scarsità idrica, ai contributi di The European House Ambrosetti in merito al Libro Bianco Valore Acqua ed al Global Prize for Water Innovation per intervento della Saudi Water Authority, è potuta emergere la centralità del gruppo di ricerca dell'Università di Palermo (di cui ResourSEAS rappresenta un chiaro esempio di successo), del modello pugliese di gestore unico AQP SpA, dell'importanza industriale del polo genovese per la costruzione di una community italiana, al servizio del Paese e del Bacino del Mediterraneo.

Secondo la Community Valore Acqua di TEHA, la dissalazione è una soluzione strategica per generare nuova risorsa idrica: si stima infatti che la capacità di produzione di acqua dissalata in Italia raggiungerà 1 milione di m3 al giorno entro il 2030.

Il WestMED National Hub Italiano ha infatti rilevato quanto la Commissione Europea abbia definito la sua strategia in materia idrica, attraverso direttive, policy papers, tassonomie, che evidenziano l'importanza del tema della dissalazione anche per la Blue Economy Sostenibile.

L'Italia, con AIDARA, può giocare un ruolo crescente in questo campo, anche in futuro.

Per informazioni scrivere a: giorgiod.maria.micale@unipa.it; associazioneaidara@gmail.com

WESTMED
blue economy initiative

Supported
by the

European
Commission

APPENDIX 7: ROLL-UP AND BROCHURES

The Project Concept

The challenges of desalination are its high energy consumption and the environmental impact of residual brine. Solar desalination solutions, combining Solar PV with Reverse Osmosis or Solar Thermal heat with Distillation, have become commercially available. Integrating brine valorization and zero liquid discharge (ZLD) aims to minimize liquid waste and close the material loop, creating a ZLD solar-powered desalination system that produces fresh water and recovers valuable resources.

SOL2H2O aims to establish a reference European facility for Circular Solar-driven Water Production & Treatment technologies, promoting renewable gas or agricultural activities.

Key Objectives

SOL2H2O unites three leading partners to boost scientific excellence in Solar-driven Water Energy Nexus solutions. By enhancing collaboration with the Widening partner, the project aims to establish a top European facility for Circular Solar-driven Water Production & Treatment technologies. A Joint Research Activity (JRA) will upgrade the Widening Research Infrastructure.

- To raise Ufèvera research profile by means of cutting-edge Joint research with EU top-tier leading partners (CEMATEC, ITC and UNIPA).
- To raise the research, technical and administrative skills of Ufèvera staff.
- To steer Career Building and attractiveness for Young Researchers to Ufèvera.
- To enhance the networking of Ufèvera in scientific and industry hubs.
- To ensure the valorization and impact of Ufèvera research.

Living in Alentejo

www.sol2h2o.uverva.pt/being-in-alentejo

Mentoring Program

SOL2H2O has a Mentoring Program that offers the opportunity to participate as either a mentor or a mentee in activities outside of work. If you are interested in signing up, simply fill out the form.

Join us!

Consortium

Solar Water Energy Nexus

Contact

Project Coordinator - Ufèvera
Dr. Pedro Horta
wh2h2o@uverva.pt

Social Media

- Twitter: @SOL2H2OEUROPE
- LinkedIn: /sol2h2o-euro
- Facebook: /ResearchInEuropeChair
- Instagram: @sol2h2o

Subscribe our Newsletter

European Twinning for research in Solar energy to (2) water (H2O) production and treatment technologies

December 2022 - November 2025

SOL2H2O

Solar Water Energy Nexus

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(2) water (H2O) production and treatment
technologies

European Twinning for research in Solar Energy to (2) water
(H2O) production and treatment technologies
GA Number: 101079305
European Research Executive Agency REA/C3

APPENDIX 8: SOCIAL MEDIA, NEWSLETTER, WEBSITE AND ZENODO NUMBERS THROUGH THE PROJECT

- Social Media

Date	LinkedIn	Twitter - X	Instagram	YouTube	Total	KPI's - good	KPI's - very good	KPI's - excellent
M1 - dec 2022						200-400	400-600	>600
M2								
M3 - feb 2023	0	0	0		0			
M4	17				17			
M5	21				21			
M6	22				22			
M7	25				25			
M8	27				27			
M9	32				32			
M10 - sep 2023	32	3	6		41			
M11	37	4	8	0	49			
M12	48	7	14	87	156			
M13	58	7	24	107	196			
M14	78				78			
M15 - feb 2024	96	40	41	115	292			
M16	132	53	46	105	336			
M17	168	56	46	148	418			
M18	191	61	50	178	480			
M19	202	69	51	203	525			
M20 - jul2024	206	58	53	222	539			
M21	210	67	54	230	561			
M22	216	60	64	253	593			
M23	219	59	63	294	635			
M24	222	25	65	346	658			
M25	223	10	64	362	659			
M26	230	10	66	419	725			
M27	235	0	70	465	770			
M28	236	0	73	502	811			
M29	239	0	74	520	833			
M30 - may 2025	241	0	76	535	852			
M31	245	0	78	567	890			
M32	248	0	78	602	928			
M33	247	0	75	625	947			
M34					0			
M35					0			
M36 - nov 2025					0			

- Newsletter

Date	Subscribers	KPI's - good	KPI's - very good	KPI's - excellent	
M1 - dec 2022					
M2					
M3					
M4					
M5					
M6					
M7					
M8		100-200	200-400	>400	
M9					
M10 - sep 2023					
M11	25				#1
M12	57				
M13	64				#2
M14	81				
M15 - feb 2024	81				#3
M16	82				
M17	84				
M18	92				#4
M19	90				#5
M20 - jul2024	91				
M21	92				#6
M22	92				
M23	106				#7
M24	106				
M25	106				#8
M26	108				#Simpósio
M27	141				#9
M28	141				
M29	141				#10
M30 - may 2025	148				
M31	163				
M32	195				#11
M33	195				#12
M34					
M35					#13
M36 - nov 2025					

- Website

Date	Visitors	KPI's - good	KPI's - very good	KPI's - excellent	
M1 - dec 2022		1000-2000	2000-3000	>3000	
M2					
M3					
M4					
M5					
M6					
M7					
M8					
M9					
M10 - sep 2023	12				
M11	98				nova versão do site
M12	125				
M13	222				
M14	277				
M15 - feb 2024	361				
M16	422				
M17	608				
M18	590				visualizations: 1889
M19	686				visualizations: 2079
M20 - jul2024	728				visualizations: 2152
M21	844				visualizations: 2373
M22	955				visualizations: 2654
M23	1071				visualizations: 2882
M24	1129				visualizations: 3017
M25	1220				visualizations: 3185
M26	1511				visualizations: 3991
M27	1706				visualizations: 4461
M28	1800				visualizations: 4702
M29	1921				visualizations: 4980
M30 - may 2025	2098				visualizations: 5232
M31	2194				visualizations: 5429
M32	2396				visualizations: 5898
M33	2480				visualizations: 6134
M34					
M35					
M36 - nov 2025					

- Zenodo

Date	Downloads	KPI's - good	PI's - very good	PI's - excellent	
M1 - dec 2022		10	30	50	
M2					
M3					
M4					
M5					
M6					
M7					
M8					
M9					
M10 - sep 2023					
M11					
M12					
M13					
M14 - jan 24	0				1st publication
M15 - feb 2024					
M16					
M17					
M18	240				
M19	316				
M20 - jul2024	327				
M21	388				
M22	389				
M23	564				
M24	639				
M25	780				
M26	814				
M27	1265				
M28	1350				
M29	1478				
M30 - may 2025	1606				
M31	1773	225 c/ acknowledgment			
M32	2100	269 c/ acknowledgment			
M33	2309	302 c/ acknowledgement	111 deliverables	415 papers	
M34					
M35					
M36 - nov 2025					